

HyDelta 3

WP1a – Asset Management – Quality assurance for local hydrogen purity specification (exit and entry)

D1a.2 – Strategies/Scenarios on how to deliver hydrogen purity in distribution networks.

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Executive summary

It is expected that in the coming years hydrogen producers and consumers will be connected via public (new-built and repurposed) transport and distribution pipelines. An important condition for setting up this system is the availability of a coordinated hydrogen specification (minimum purity, allowed trace components and bandwidth for Wobbe index) for infeeders and off-takers at all pressure levels in the networks.

Defining a hydrogen quality network specification is a complex task, in which many interests need to be weighed against each other against a background of various techno economical limitations and possible technical solutions. In the Netherlands, first insights about a hydrogen specification in transmission and distribution level have been published. For the Dutch high-pressure transport network, operated by Hynetwork (HN), a concept specification has been published (not adopted yet) by the Ministry of Climate Policy and Green Growth. For the regional distribution networks a first explorative hydrogen specification has been formulated in 2021.

This HyDelta work package aims to provide further insights (both technically and economically) into **feasible specifications for hydrogen distribution grids**¹ in order to support operators in substantiating their strategies for feed-in, offtake and monitoring and controlling the agreed hydrogen quality. The insights delivered in this HyDelta research project can be used as basis for the development of an entry and exit specification for hydrogen in the Dutch distribution networks.

The research activities focus on the following elements:

- A. A techno economic analysis to deliver insights on the preferred hydrogen purity level for distribution networks from a market cost point of view
- B. A technical infrastructural analysis to deliver insight on the technical network limitations, e.g. the effects of permeation and desorption on hydrogen quality in distribution networks
- C. How to manage hydrogen quality in future hydrogen networks (combining inputs from part A and B), including an infeed monitoring and measurement protocol

The result of each element of the research is summarized below.

A. Techno-economic analysis for the regional distribution networks

For techno-economic market modelling analyses of the optimal hydrogen purity level in regional gas distribution networks, a hydrogen purity cost model was developed based on a methodology used in a previous study performed for the ministry of Economic Affairs. A techno-economic analysis was performed using the model for two regional distribution network types (both in the range from 1-16 bar): a harbour area and a rural area, including their interactions with the Hynetwork system. The model uses seven production/consumption scenarios (volume, type of customer etc.) for the years 2035 and 2050. All producers and off-takers are connected to the network including their respective produced and required purity level. Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) has been applied as the key hydrogen purification technology, which produces, besides high purity hydrogen, also a tail gas stream including the filtered-out impurities. The model provides insight into the optimal purity specification (sweet spot) of hydrogen in the regional distribution networks from a societal perspective based on realistic scenarios about the development of the hydrogen market.

¹ High pressure distribution network (1-16 bar – repurposed and newly build steel and PE pipelines) / Low pressure distribution/network (30-200 mbar – repurposed and new PE and PVC pipelines)

From a pure market cost point of view following conclusion can be deducted:

- **a future-proof sweet spot for high pressure distribution networks (1-16 bar) is between 98% and 99.5%.**

- for the harbour network case study, a future proof market sweet spot for the grid purity level is between 98% and 99.7%.
- for the rural network case study, a technically feasible sweet spot is between 98% and 99.5%.

- Generally speaking, overall purification related costs in the sweet spot range are expected to be ~0.1 €/kg transported hydrogen. Outside the sweet spot range the cost level is a factor 2-3 higher.
- **it is most optimal to keep the hydrogen purity level in regional gas 1-16 bar distribution levels identical to the HN specification given the fact that:**
 - this provides the most freedom for interchangeability (boosting or intaking) of hydrogen with the Hynetwork grid, independent of the (to be determined) HN specification
 - the 98% -99.5% purity level will be acceptable to both the bulk of the hydrogen end-users as well as the bulk of the hydrogen producers.

B. Technical analysis of the effects of permeation and desorption on hydrogen purity

In order to understand how Dutch distribution grids (build from steel, PE and PVC pipeline material) can influence the distributed and delivered hydrogen purity, a technical model has been developed to calculate the effect of permeation (through PE and PVC) for the high pressure distribution grid (1-8 bar) and low pressure (30-200 mbar) sections. The focus hereby lies on the permeation of components from the environment (oxygen, nitrogen and water). Solid components such as (mining) dust and solid components from the soil have no influence on the gas quality. Other liquid or gaseous contaminants that can enter during construction (drilling fluid) or maintenance work, or through cracks or fractures as a result of incidents, have not been included in this study.

The permeation modelling unveils that:

- **at higher pressures (>1 bar) the impact of permeation on hydrogen purity is limited** as there is less incoming contamination (due to the greater wall thickness) and more gas inside the pipeline (due to the higher pressure) in which it mixes. It should be noted that for repurposed pipelines on 1-8 bar level there are some challenges related to existing contaminations. Further research is needed on this.
- **the largest effects of permeation are in the low-pressure networks (30-200 mbar).** Especially when there is (almost) no flow (comparable with the current natural gas offtake in summer), permeation can lead to a significant amount of impurities which affects the hydrogen purity.

Additionally, it was concluded that **the effect of desorption is limited to the starting period of the pipeline lifecycle**, which can be solved by agreements with customers or technical solutions. THT, used for odorization of natural gas, could pose a challenge when using repurposed pipelines, especially if the end-user utilizes a fuel cell. If this use-case presents itself, it should be further investigated.

C. Managing hydrogen quality in future hydrogen networks

Bringing together the above presented market techno-economic track (part A) and infrastructure technical material track (part B) a first concept of managing future hydrogen distribution networks will unveil. The basic idea is that for hydrogen quality management purposes the distribution network is divided in two clusters with different purity specifications.

➤ Cluster 1: on same purity level as HN system

As mentioned before, it is preferable to keep the hydrogen purity level in regional gas distribution levels on 1 - 16 bar on the same purity specifications as the HN specification given the fact this provides the most freedom when boosting or importing hydrogen to/from HN and the 98%-99.5% level will be acceptable to both majority of end users and producers.

The above findings are certainly true for new networks to be installed (both plastic and steel) on 1-16 bar level. For the reused pipelines of 1-8 bar (steel, PE and PVC), there is insufficient certainty about the feasibility as pipelines in these network may contain trace components. This is in the above figure indicated by a question mark in the box “repurposed pipelines”.

Specific attention for cluster 1 is needed for the reverse flow option from distribution network towards transmission level. It is expected that it will become legally mandatory to odorize hydrogen in distribution networks (just like for natural gas). This legal obligation does not apply to transport networks. When boosting from the distribution network to the transport network, it is necessary to include a de-odorization step. Further insights in the technology readiness and cost of such technology is needed.

➤ Cluster 2: at lower purity level

As discussed above, the permeation effect in low pressure networks (30-200 mbar) has much more impact on the hydrogen purity compared to the high pressure distribution network. Especially in situations with (almost) no flow (comparable with the current natural gas offtake in summer). For this reason the purity level in the low pressure network should be on a different level. In the picture above indicated with “cluster 2”. As a consequence of the different purity levels in cluster 1 and cluster 2 reverse flow from low pressure distribution networks towards the high pressure distribution network is not expected to be possible. And, as the capacity of the low pressure distribution network is rather limited local infeed is restricted as well.

Once the entry- and exit specifications are defined, a solid **infeed protocol to monitor and measure the hydrogen for (local) producers is needed**. Based on available hydrogen specifications and building on the Dutch biomethane infeed protocol, this HyDelta study provides the first building blocks for the regulatory and technical aspects of a Measuring and Control Protocol for hydrogen.

Managementsamenvatting

Naar verwachting zullen in de komende jaren waterstofproducenten en -consumenten met elkaar verbonden worden via openbare (nieuwe en hergebruikte) waterstof transport- en distributieleidingen. Een belangrijke voorwaarde voor het opzetten van dit systeem is een afgestemde waterstofsificatie (minimale zuiverheid, toegestane sporencomponenten en bandbreedte voor Wobbe-index) voor invoeders en afnemers op alle drukkiveaus in de netwerken.

Het definiëren van een netwerk-specificatie voor waterstof is een complexe opgave, waarbij diverse belangen tegen elkaar moeten worden afgewogen tegen een achtergrond van verschillende techno-economische beperkingen en mogelijke technische oplossingen. In Nederland zijn de eerste inzichten over waterstofsificaties in transport- en distributieniveau gepubliceerd. Voor het Nederlandse hogedruktransportnet, geëxploiteerd door Hynetwork (HN) is er een conceptspecificatie gepubliceerd (nog niet vastgesteld) door het ministerie van Klimaat en Groene Groei; KGG) Voor de regionale distributienetten is een eerste verkennende waterstofsificatie geformuleerd in 2021.

Dit HyDelta-werkpakket heeft als doel om meer inzicht (zowel technisch als economisch) te bieden in **haalbare specificaties voor waterstof distributienetten**² om daarmee operators te ondersteunen bij het onderbouwen van hun strategieën voor invoeding, afname en het bewaken en beheersen van de overeengekomen waterstofkwaliteit. De inzichten uit dit HyDelta onderzoeksproject kunnen worden gebruikt als basis voor de ontwikkeling van entry- en exit specificaties voor waterstof in de Nederlandse distributienetten.

De onderzoeksactiviteiten richten zich op de volgende drie elementen:

- A. Een technisch-economische analyse om inzicht te krijgen in de gewenste waterstofzuiverheidsniveau voor de distributienetwerken vanuit het oogpunt van marktkosten;
- B. Een technisch-infrastructuur analyse om technische netwerkbeperkingen ten aanzien van de impact van permeatie en desorptie op de waterstofkwaliteit in distributienetwerken te begrijpen;
- C. Opzet en beheer van de waterstofkwaliteit in toekomstige waterstofnetwerken (combineren van input uit deel A en B) inclusief een monitoring- en meetprotocol voor waterstof invoeders

Het resultaat van elk onderdeel van het onderzoek wordt hieronder samengevat.

A. Techno-economische analyse voor de regionale distributienetten

Voor techno-economische marktmodelleringsanalyses van het optimale waterstofzuiverheidsniveau in regionale gasdistributienetten is een kostenmodel voor waterstofzuiverheid ontwikkeld op basis van een methodologie die eerder is gebruikt in een onderzoek dat is uitgevoerd in opdracht van het ministerie van Economische Zaken. Met behulp van het model is een techno-economische analyse uitgevoerd voor twee regionale 1-16 bar distributienetwerktypen: een havengebied en een landelijk gebied, inclusief hun interacties met het Hynetwork-systeem. Het model maakt gebruik van zeven productie-/consumptiescenario's (volume, type klant etc.) voor de jaren 2035 en 2050. Alle producenten en afnemers zijn aangesloten op het netwerk, inclusief hun respectieve geproduceerde en vereiste zuiverheidsniveau. Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) is toegepast als de belangrijkste waterstofzuiveringstechnologie, die naast zeer zuivere waterstof ook een restgasstroom produceert inclusief de uitgefilterde onzuiverheden. Het model geeft inzicht in de optimale zuiverheidsspecificatie (sweet spot) van waterstof in de regionale distributienetten gezien vanuit de samenleving op basis van realistische scenario's over de ontwikkeling van de waterstofmarkt.

² Hogedruk distributienetwerk (1-16 bar – hergebruikte en nieuwe staal- en PE-leidingen) / Lagedruk distributienetwerk (30-200 mbar – hergebruikte en nieuwe PE- en PVC-leidingen)

Uit deze techno-economische marktmodellering kan worden geconcludeerd dat:

- **Een toekomstbestendige sweet spot voor hogedruk distributienetwerken (1-16 bar) in de range van 98% tot 99,5% ligt.**

- Voor de casus havennetwerk ligt de sweet spot van het zuiverheidsniveau van het net tussen 98% en 99,7%.
- Voor de casus landelijk netwerk, waar een technisch haalbare sweet spot tussen 98% en 99,5% ligt.

- Over het algemeen wordt verwacht dat de totale kosten voor zuivering in het sweet spot-bereik $\sim 0,1$ €/kg getransporteerde waterstof zullen bedragen. Buiten de sweet spot range is het kostenniveau een factor 2-3 hoger.
- Vanuit het oogpunt van marktkosten is **het meest optimale waterstofzuiverheidsniveau in regionale gasdistributienetten (1-16 bar) identiek aan de HN-specificatie** gezien het feit dat:
 - Dit de meeste vrijheid geeft voor het uitwisselen (afnemen dan wel terug leveren) van waterstof met het Hynetwork-net, onafhankelijk van de (nog vast te stellen) HN-specificatie.
 - Het zuiverheidsniveau in de range van 98%-99,5% aanvaardbaar zal zijn voor zowel het grootste deel van de eindgebruikers van waterstof als ook het grootste deel van de waterstofproducenten.

B. Technische analyse van de effecten van permeatie en desorptie op de zuiverheid van waterstof

Om te begrijpen hoe Nederlandse distributienetten (opgebouwd uit staal, PE en PVC leidingmateriaal) invloed kunnen hebben op de gedistribueerde en geleverde waterstofzuiverheid, is een model ontwikkeld om het effect van permeatie (door PE en PVC) te berekenen voor het hogedruk distributienetwerk (1-8 bar) en lage druk (30-200 mbar) secties. Hierbij wordt gefocust op de permeatie van componenten uit de omgeving (zuurstof, stikstof en water). Vaste componenten als (mijn) stof, componenten uit de bodem hebben geen invloed op de gaskwaliteit. Andere verontreinigingen die binnen kunnen dringen tijdens aanleg (boorvloeistof) of onderhoudswerkzaamheden, of via scheuren of breuken als gevolg van incidenten, zijn niet in dit onderzoek meegenomen. De modellering laat zien dat:

- **bij hogere drukken (>1 bar) is de impact van permeatie op de zuiverheid van waterstof beperkt** omdat er minder inkomende verontreiniging is (door de grotere wanddikte) en meer gas in de pijpleiding (door de hogere druk) waarin het mengt. Opgemerkt moet worden dat er voor hergebruikte pijpleidingen op een niveau van 1-8 bar enkele uitdagingen zijn die verband houden met bestaande verontreinigingen. Hier is verder onderzoek nodig.
- **de grootste effecten van permeatie doen zich voor in de lagedruk netwerken (30-200 mbar).** Vooral wanneer er (bijna) geen doorstroming is (vergelijkbaar met de huidige aardgasafname in de zomer) kan permeatie leiden tot een aanzienlijke hoeveelheid onzuiverheden en daarmee de waterstofzuiverheid beïnvloeden.

Daarnaast werd geconcludeerd dat **het effect van desorptie beperkt is tot de beginperiode van de levenscyclus van de pijpleiding**, die kan worden opgelost door afspraken met aangesloten klanten overeenkomsten of technische oplossingen. THT, verantwoordelijk voor de odorisatie van aardgas, kan een uitdaging vormen bij het gebruik van hergebruikte pijpleidingen, vooral als de eindgebruiker een brandstofcel gebruikt. Als deze situatie zich voordoet, is verder onderzoek nodig.

C. Beheer van de waterstofkwaliteit in toekomstige waterstofnetwerken

Door de hierboven gepresenteerde techno-economische marktstudie (deel A) en de infrastructuur technische materiaalstudie (deel B) samen te brengen, zal een eerste concept voor het beheer van toekomstige waterstofdistributienetwerken worden ontsloten. De basisgedachte is dat het distributienet voor het beheer van de waterstofkwaliteit verdeeld is in twee clusters met verschillende zuiverheid specificaties.

➤ Cluster 1: op het zelfde zuiverheidsniveau als het HN-netwerk

Zoals hierboven beschreven, verdient het de voorkeur om het waterstofzuiverheidsniveau in regionale gasdistributieniveaus op 1 - 16 bar dicht bij de HN-specificatie te houden, aangezien dit de meeste vrijheid biedt bij het uitwisselen van waterstof met het HN-netwerk en de range van 98%-99,5% acceptabel is voor het grootste deel van de eindgebruikers als de producenten.

Bovenstaande bevindingen gelden zeker voor nieuw aan te leggen netwerken (zowel kunststof als staal) op 1-16 bar niveau. Voor hergebruikte leidingen van 1-8 bar (staal, PE en PVC) is er onvoldoende zekerheid over de haalbaarheid van een vastgelegde waterstofzuiverheid, aangezien leidingen in dit netwerk sporencomponenten kunnen bevatten. Dit is in de bovenstaande figuur aangegeven door een vraagteken in het vak "hergebruikte pijpleidingen".

Specifieke aandacht voor cluster 1 is nodig rondom teruglevering van waterstof (reverse-flow) van het distributienetwerk naar het HN transportniveau. Verwacht wordt dat het wettelijk verplicht wordt om waterstof in distributienetten (net als voor aardgas) te odoriseren. Voor transportnetten is deze wettelijke verplichting er niet. Bij terugleveren vanuit het distributienet naar het transportnetwerk, is het noodzakelijk een de-odorisatie stap in te bouwen. Er is meer inzicht nodig in de technologische gereedheid en kosten van dergelijke technologie.

➤ Cluster 2: op een lager zuiverheidsniveau

Zoals hierboven besproken, heeft het permeatie-effect in lagedruk netwerken (30-200 mbar) veel meer impact op de waterstofzuiverheid in vergelijking met het hogedruk distributienetwerk. Zeker in situaties met (bijna) geen doorstroming (vergelijkbaar met de huidige aardgasafname in de zomer). Om deze reden moet het zuiverheidsniveau in het lagedruknetwerk op een ander niveau liggen. Dit is in bovenstaande figuur aangegeven met "cluster 2". Als gevolg van de verschillende zuiverheidsniveaus in cluster 1 en cluster 2 is terug leveren vanuit het lagedruk distributienet naar het hogedruk distributienet naar verwachting niet mogelijk. Ook is de mogelijkheid om lokaal in te voeden beperkt omdat de capaciteit van het lagedruk distributienet beperkt is.

Zodra de entry- en exit-specificaties zijn gedefinieerd, is een solide **invoedingsprotocol** nodig **om de waterstof van (lokale) invoerders te monitoren en te meten**. Op basis van beschikbare waterstof-specificaties en voortbouwend op het Nederlandse invoedingsprotocol voor biomethaan, biedt deze HyDelta-studie de eerste bouwstenen voor de regelgevende en technische aspecten van een meet- en regelprotocol voor waterstof.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Developing a hydrogen market

The implementation of hydrogen in existing gas networks in the Netherlands is currently taking important steps forward: e.g., Hynetwork is developing a national hydrogen backbone; regional distribution companies are learning intensively from hydrogen pilot projects; and energy intensive industries are exploring the options to make their production processes more sustainable with hydrogen. Having a clear and transparent hydrogen quality specification is crucial to facilitate market players, guarantee the pipeline integrity and to guarantee optimal and safe performance of end-use equipment.

At national level, Hynetwork (HN) is building the hydrogen network to connect the major industrial regions. The future distribution grids are expected to be divided into three levels: a high-pressure grid (8-16 bar) high-pressure grid (1-8) and a low-pressure grid (30-200 mbar), in the basis similar to the natural gas grid. Industrial customers, hydrogen production and import technologies are connected to the high-pressure grid, which is expected to consist of newly built steel or reused PVC/steel pipelines. Also, the high-pressure distribution grid is expected to be soon connected (bidirectionally) to the hydrogen transmission network. Residential and small businesses are connected to the 30-200 mbar low-pressure grid that consists of reused existing gas infrastructure (PE/PVC pipelines).

An important parameter in connecting the numerous customers and hydrogen suppliers is the hydrogen quality. An indicative hydrogen specification for this high-pressure transmission grid has been published, but at present no developments are ongoing to develop a hydrogen specification for the gas distribution networks.

In a further developing a hydrogen market, the gas distribution networks are crucial hubs connecting numerous end-users and local hydrogen suppliers while re-using existing gas infrastructure or building new infrastructure. The distribution network operators need to understand all sources impacting the outgoing hydrogen quality towards end-users. Operators need insight into the extent to which existing (re-used) gas infrastructure is able to deliver the correct purity of hydrogen to the customer, per grid level, or at the transfer point, and what technological challenges there are for the delivery of the right (contracted) hydrogen quality.

1.2 Key elements for defining an hydrogen quality specifications

The ultimate goal is to find a balanced hydrogen quality standard in which the end user is protected and receives the required hydrogen quality and at the same time to avoid unnecessarily strict specifications, which leads to high costs for the local hydrogen producers and hydrogen network operators. When developing specifications the following elements should be considered:

1. End-user hydrogen requirements

End-users do not all have the same requirements for hydrogen purity. Some end-users need high purity levels (e.g. 99.9+%) while others accept 95% purity level. The required hydrogen quality from the perspective of the end-user strongly depends on the end-user's application.

2. Local hydrogen production and hydrogen quality produced.

In a future mature hydrogen network, small- and medium-sized hydrogen suppliers will be connected to the regional network [1]. Hydrogen produced with various production technologies (SMR, electrolysis, gasification, and possibly new technologies) will be fed into the gas network. Operators therefore need to understand the composition of locally produced hydrogen and the specific trace components. Different hydrogen production technologies may have different profiles for impurities and trace components causing risks for the hydrogen purity/quality in the network.

3. Purification technologies Storage and cross border trade

In addition to end use, supply and transport, a fully functioning hydrogen system also requires storage and cross border trade. Hydrogen will need to be stored for short term balancing of intermittent green supply, bridge seasonal supply-demand imbalances and eventually also for security of supply purposes. To this end a mix of line pack, salt caverns, depleted gas fields and aquifers will be used. These storages may be newly build or repurposed natural gas storages. The new salt caverns will likely be able to send out higher hydrogen purity grades but new and repurposed depleted gas fields and aquifer will struggle with impurities. In addition to storage, hydrogen will be exchanged between European countries and thus a European hydrogen purity standard will need to be agreed upon.

4. Purification technologies

In case purity levels need to be increased or trace components removed, purification or filtering technologies can be applied at production sides as well as at end-user locations. Different technologies are available; some are mature while others are still under development. For network operators it is therefore important to understand all (potentially) available technologies for hydrogen purification.

5. New and re-used infrastructure

Existing gas infrastructure can be re-used for hydrogen distribution networks. However, re-using existing infrastructure poses a number of challenges for hydrogen purity. The pollution already present in the network may have an(temporary) effect on the outgoing purity due partially to the higher hydrogen flow rates (trace components, dust, and other contaminants). Also, the permeability of the pipeline material used needs to be further investigated to understand, for example, the permeation of nitrogen and oxygen into hydrogen-transporting PE pipes. The Dutch hydrogen pilots for the built environment may serve as an excellent learning environment for these issues.

6. Monitoring & Control

Once the hydrogen quality standards have been developed options and scenarios have to be developed to deliver the desired/contracted hydrogen quality to the end-user at the lowest costs. Important element is here how hydrogen infeed form producers has to be monitored and controlled.

1.3 Objective of this work

The objective of this work package is to deliver the building blocks that can be used as basis for the development of an entry and exit specification for hydrogen quality in Dutch distribution networks including a first draft of the monitoring and control protocol. Such a protocol has been developed for green gas and could be adapted for hydrogen.

The main research questions for this HyDelta work package on hydrogen specifications are:

1. What hydrogen quality is needed for specific end-user applications?
2. What risks in terms of pollution and impurities are to be expected from existing and still developing hydrogen production technologies feeding into the gas distribution grid? In this context also the connection between the Hynetwork transmission system and the distribution networks can be considered as a feed-in point (e.g., at the gas receiving station).
3. What are the risks in terms of the resulting hydrogen quality when re-using existing steel, PE or PVC pipelines?
4. What technologies are available for purification/filtering of hydrogen supplied at different locations in the network?
5. Which options and scenarios do regional grid operators have to deliver the desired/contracted hydrogen purity at the lowest overall purification costs and what monitoring and control protocols are needed?

This work package is split into two phases; in phase 1 a literature study was performed on the following elements (see [2] for more details):

- Hydrogen quality requirements of end-users
- Inventory of impurities caused by various hydrogen production technologies
- Hydrogen purification technologies – state of the art

In this report the results of phase 2 of this work package are discussed, which include;

- **Overall hydrogen purification costs in relation to the hydrogen purity.** Based on the input from phase 1, a hydrogen market cost model was developed to perform a high-level techno-economic analysis for seven production and off-take scenarios in a distribution network for the years 2035 and 2050. Two cases have been considered; an industrial harbour region and a rural regional area.
- **The effect of permeation on the hydrogen gas quality.** To study the effect of air and water permeation (into plastic pipes) on the hydrogen quality delivered to the end-user, a model has been developed. Both high- and low-pressure distribution grids are considered. The calculations are performed for two areas; an urban and a rural area, where in the rural area the distances between connections are larger. Also, the effect of a summer holiday, where the gas flow is stopped for 14 days, is taken as a research case.
- **The effect of desorption on the hydrogen gas quality.** In repurposed gas pipeline, trace components present in natural gas may be absorbed in the pipe wall. These components may slowly desorb into hydrogen and effect the hydrogen quality delivered to the end-user. A model has been developed to calculate desorption of alkanes and THT in time for different pipeline materials.
- **Building blocks/requirements for a monitoring and control protocol.** Based on the protocols developed for green gas, the building blocks for a future monitoring and control protocol are described.

2. Hydrogen purity model: techno-economic considerations for hydrogen purity

2.1 Introduction

In 2023, KIWA and DNV performed a study on behalf of the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs on the “techno-economic optimal hydrogen purity specifications for the Dutch hydrogen system” [3, 4]. The focus of this study was on the optimal hydrogen purity in the future Dutch national transport systems and to list the techno-economic pros and cons of “>98%” versus “>99.5%” hydrogen purity standard. To quantify the overall cost impact of “98% versus 99.5% minimum purity requirement”, a hydrogen purity cost model has been created, based on a concept model developed in an (Gasunie internal) previous study, as illustrated in figure 2.1. This conceptual model was tailored to meet the specific requirements of the stakeholders of the future Dutch hydrogen systems.

Figure 2.1 conceptual diagram of techno-economic model: The impact of a 98% v 99.5% minimum hydrogen purity requirement on a national hydrogen network visually illustrated here via the “red dots”. A “red dot” represents a purification stage that needs to be installed to align either an end user or producer with the hydrogen specification of the backbone system. A purification stage will however introduce extra costs and economic losses to the system and the challenge for the model is to identify the optimal set of purification measures.

In the EZK study, the following model input information and validated them with market stakeholders have been collected:

- Alignment on the hydrogen purity model scope concerning suppliers (on shore/ offshore electrolyzers, blue hydrogen, ammonia & LOHC importers), end users (power plants, industrial heat, chemical feedstock, mobility, residential), hydrogen transport (road transport, pipeline, distribution, transit Belgium/ Germany) and storage (salt caverns)
- Minimum hydrogen purity requirements of current and future end user categories.
- Minimum hydrogen purity abilities of current and future suppliers without additional purification steps.
- A set of 2035 and 2050 hydrogen supply-demand scenarios, covering the technological range of technologies in scope and future price levels.
- The techno-economic impact of installing and operating “Pressure Swing Adsorption” (PSA) hydrogen purification stages and especially the ability to find useful application for the so-called “tail gas”, a small low pressure flow out of the PSA’s containing the filtered-out impurities and small amounts of hydrogen [2].

Based on the agreed Hydrogen purity model scope and technical parameters, the model outputs a “spectrum of cost curves” for the input scenarios as outlined in figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: results EZK study: characteristic “curve spectrum” of the hydrogen purity cost model: total hydrogen purity related costs (normalized per kg), as a function of the minimum hydrogen purity requirement of the future hydrogen system, differentiated for a seven market scenarios).

Based on the “spectrum of cost curves” it is possible to identify so-called “sweet spots” in hydrogen purity requirements for the national hydrogen system, including the robustness of the “sweet spot” across a wide range of uncertainties, such as market scenarios and technical assumptions.

For this HyDelta 3 work package, the hydrogen purity cost model from the EZK study was used as basis for a model specifically developed for the regional hydrogen networks. The following approach was chosen:

- We started with conceptual frameworks as outlined in figure 2.1.
- We collected information on future market scenarios and technical specifications of future suppliers, end users and networks designs.
- We aligned with DSO experts on the envisaged ambitions for the regional hydrogen networks in a workshop and online progress reports.
- We created an updated hydrogen purity cost model to include all new information and requirements.
- We aligned the findings with DSO experts in a workshop session.

The main research questions are as follows:

- From a societal perspective, what is the **optimal purity** hydrogen specification in the regional transmission networks based on realistic scenarios on the hydrogen market developments?
- What are the key market trends and technical drivers for the optimal purity and how robust are the findings?

Note that in this work we will refer to hydrogen purity specifications only on high level terms i.e. “98% v. 99.5%” and not go into technical detail on the allowed impurities that make up the remaining 2% or 0.5%. The outcome of this work can serve as a basis for the future development of entry and exit specifications for hydrogen quality in the Dutch regional hydrogen network.

2.1.1 Lessons learned from natural gas

To better understand to what extent gas specifications can ultimately impact the development on a gas market, we can take lessons from the Dutch natural gas network. The natural gas specifications of the Dutch natural gas systems arose in the following stages:

- The Dutch natural gas system was built in the early 1960’s out to transport gas from the Groningen-field to residential and industrial customers in the Netherlands, Belgium, West-Germany and Northern France. The Groningen field however produced a very specific type of low calorific natural gas (“G-gas”) and Dutch distribution market was set to this specific G-gas standard and international customers to the wider “L-gas” specification. The narrow G-gas band allowed Dutch customers to achieve higher boiler efficiency and lower emissions whereas the wider bandwidth allowed Belgium, Germany to be more flexible in sourcing natural gas.
- With the subsequent discovery of small fields, the Dutch natural gas system was split up in parallel gas networks tasked with 1) delivering G-gas to Dutch distribution markets, 2) delivering L-gas to Belgium and Germany, 3) take in various “off spec” gasses from on-shore and off-shore small fields, 4) transit LNG (H⁺ gas) and H-gas from Norway and Russia to UK, Belgium, Germany. The parallel gas networks interconnected at gas blending stations, including nitrogen ballasting, to create all the specific specifications for specific end user markets. The great flexibility in converting gas qualities was one of the reasons for the success of the Netherlands as the “European gas roundabout” and the positioning of the TTF as the leading European trading Hub. Figure 2.3 illustrates the resulting complex network
- However, with the closure of the Groningen field a large nitrogen production site in Zuidbroek was built to supply Pseudo G-gas from H-gas to the Dutch market [5]

This illustrates the impact gas specifications can have in the evolution of the market. As a rule, strict gas specifications are beneficial for end users, allowing for higher efficiencies and lower emissions, i.e. higher willingness to pay, but pose challenges to producers and the TSO/ DSO. Wider gas specifications allow for more diverse supply mix and increased system robustness, creating more competition and lower prices and less challenges to TSO/ DSO’s. But wider specifications also pose market barriers to “premium” end users such as industry feedstock and especially (fuel-cell based) mobility. Gas specification choices can thus create market status quos for decades that once set in motion are very hard to adjust.

In this work we will however purely focus on quantifying the total market cost of all required gas treatment plants placed either at suppliers, DSO’s and end users to maintain specific *regional* gas specifications. This is the scope of the Hydrogen purity cost model. We will however not quantify the associated decades long market costs/ benefits such as barriers to new producers or end users for various hydrogen specifications nor the financial benefits of increased security of supply, as they are highly challenging to quantify. Instead, we will address them in a more qualitative manner.

Figure 2.3: the Dutch natural gas network including Nitrogen (red), low calorific G-gas and L-gas (grey) and H-gas yellow.

2.2 Hydrogen purity cost model

In the period from 2019-2021 DNV has investigated together with N.V. Nederlandse Gasunie in various ways to quantify the market impacts of possible national hydrogen network purity standard. This eventually resulted in a concept “Hydrogen purity cost model”, that aimed to weigh the following factors:

- Possible hydrogen network design options & quality specifications.
- Volume of future hydrogen suppliers and end users.
- The impact of PSA purification stages.
- Total purification related costs for specific hydrogen quality specifications.

The core concept of the model is that appropriate measures will need to be taken somewhere along the supply chain, pre-emptively at the side of the suppliers, or just-in-time by the end users or even halfway the system by TSO or DSO to keep the overall hydrogen system within its specifications. The associated costs made by any party will be reflected in one form or another in the overall hydrogen price. The key issue is to determine which players are best positioned to take potentially costly technical measures to keep the overall purification related costs as low as possible. Towards this end the following guidelines are considered:

- Minimize the possibilities that hydrogen is purified twice, both by the supplier and the end user.
- Minimize possibilities that hydrogen is unnecessarily purified by the supplier, i.e. bulk of the end users could have been better served with “cheaper lower quality” hydrogen.
- Concentrate the purification measures with the players who are best equipped to handle this purification task with the most economy of scale and with high annual load factors.
- Also concentrate hydrogen purification at market parties with a direct use for energy content of the so-called “tail gas” out of the separators, i.e. the “off spec” hydrogen flow containing the filtered-out impurities that will need to be burned locally by a specialized burner.
- The network must be balanced to account for all tail gas losses.

The original model was considered an internal “proof of concept” model for Gasunie internal policy purposes only. However, given the wide interest in this topic by the stakeholders, a fully revised version of the original model was made for the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs (the “EZK” model) and this model was again fully revised to meet the specific needs of this HyDelta Work Package, the future Dutch regional hydrogen networks.

2.2.1 Model description

The Hydrogen purity cost model is an “MS Excel “bookkeeping model using macro’s”, set up according to the conceptual design illustrated in figure 2.1. The calculation engine calculates the hydrogen purity related costs for the following inputs:

- possible hydrogen network purity standards,
- a specific market volume & price scenario
- a specific set of default technical input parameters,
- alternative datasets to test the robustness of the result for uncertainties in input values.

Figure 2.4: model flow: the data flow through the main hydrogen purity cost model: first a specific set of market scenarios, technical parameters and prices is prepared and then transferred to the calculation engine. The Calculation Engine then determines the hydrogen purity related costs (tail gas, CAPEX, OPEX) for suppliers, end users or the TSO/ DSO interfacing between the regional network and the national network (HN)

The actual model data and calculation flow is illustrated in figure 2.4. The main model premise is that all suppliers and end users are connected to “stirred vessel” hydrogen system with a specific minimum hydrogen purity specification, ranging from a possibly very low (<95%) to very high (>99.99%) specification. The model then calculates the overall market impact of a specific purity specification on all individual market segments: suppliers, national Transmission System Operators (TSO), local Distribution System Operators (DSO), as they need to decide to invest in separation/ purification measures (mainly PSA systems) in order to be fully compatible with a specific network purity standard.

The final calculation step in the model calculation is to re-balance the original supply-demand scenario to account for all the tail gas losses. When the regional network is connected to Dutch TSO called “Hynetwork” (HN), this will result in additional hydrogen deliveries or supplies to/from HN. In case of standalone network, we will rebalance via additional production (LOHC is mostly chosen as the default balancing supplier) or additional industrial end use, where we assume that a large baseload industrial end user can either switch between hydrogen delivery from HN and the regional network or even switch back to natural gas.

The overall cost impact is that whenever a separation/ purification stage is introduced, CAPEX investment and operational expenditures (maintenance and electricity) will need to be made and the associated “tail gas”, a small hydrogen flow including the filtered impurities, will need to be disposed off locally. The main issue is that tail gas can only be used locally as a source of heat and thus may represent the following economic loss factors:

- For **suppliers**, tail gas represents a missed opportunity to sell more valuable hydrogen to the market and use an alternative, more cost effective, energy source to meet local heat demands.
- For **end users**, tail gas production implies the purchase of more valuable hydrogen from the market instead of using industrial waste heat or an alternative, more cost effective, energy source to meet local heat demands.
- For **TSO/ DSO's** the challenge is to find a local industrial end user for tail gas associated with either purifying hydrogen from the HN system, or boosting “off spec” regional hydrogen to the HN system.

To quantify these economic “loss of value” associated with tail gas, the remaining heat content is compared to the lowest cost alternative heat source, assumed to be natural gas + CO₂ emission rights. In 2035, it is mainly the price spread between hydrogen v. natural gas+CO₂ emission rights that drives the overall tail gas associated economic losses. This implies that in 2035, when hydrogen is still considered a premium energy source compared to natural gas, the tail gas economic losses, as *measured in €/kg*, will be high. In 2050, when hydrogen is expected to be a direct alternative to natural gas, the tail gas economic losses, measured in €/kg, will be low. However, due to the increase in the overall hydrogen market volume in 2050, the total market “tail gas economic losses” are likely to still be high, when compared to 2035.

The full scope of the model data organization around the hydrogen purity cost model is illustrated in figure 2.5. Note that the model facilitates a very wide range of possible data input combinations. A full model run may comprise the following market narrative, as illustrated in figure 2.6: *“calculate the Hydrogen purity costs for a **harbor** network in 2050, for a **tree** type network topology **without** a connection to HN, for the **European Integration** scenario, apply a “**clean supply / dirty demand**” bias/ variant to the default market split and include a **positive** parameter bias”*. Each choice however has a default value and a set of alternatives to test the sensitivity to the uncertainties. The model uses macros to automate the run calculations.

Figure 2.5: model organization: data organization around the hydrogen purity cost model, as outlined in figure 3, here shown in red. There are additional data sections preparing the general input data, including prices specific for the scenarios chosen and HyDelta specific assumptions on key technical parameters and their uncertainties, a data preparations stage and macros to automate the running of all possible sets of input combinations.

Figure 2.6: model run. A model run consists of a series of options concerning network scope, 2035/ 2050 market scenario's, market split across HN/ Harbor/ Rural networks and uncertainties in the technical parameters. The default values are indicated in **bold** font.

It is also important to note that the developed hydrogen purity cost model is a highly simplified techno-economic model and treats cost factors in the following way:

- Cost only include the CAPEX/ OPEX/ tail gas purification costs of the market players, i.e. producers, end users and TSO/ DSO/storage operators.
- Annual CAPEX of separation stages is defined as CAPEX / technical lifetime.
- OPEX (annual maintenance + electric power use) assumed as a fixed rate of CAPEX (typically ~5%)
- No inflation correction, no interest rates, commodity price discovery, taxes or subsidies.
- No re-use of existing PSA or other separation installations as their technical status is unknown. All 2035 and 2050 investments are considered green field, even in 2050.

The main purpose of the model is thus to provide insights into the key drivers for determining the optimal network specification and the model costs should not be used outside this context. The hydrogen purity cost model, like other models, is a simplification of a real system, which means that hydrogen purity cost model used in this work has limitations. More information on these limitations can be found in Appendix A.

2.3 Input parameters

In this section we will discuss all the input parameters used by the hydrogen purity cost model.

2.3.1 Network scopes

When discussing the hydrogen purity specification of regional networks, we first have to define what regional networks could look like. In this HyDelta 3 work package we identified the following network scopes (Figure 2.7):

- Hynetwork, the national hydrogen system
- Harbor networks
- Rural networks
- Road transport directly to mobility filling stations

Figure 2.7: network sketch of the HN/ Harbor/ Rural networks and road transports connecting electrolyzers and mobility filling stations.

Hynetwork (HN)

Hynetwork is currently creating a national hydrogen network for the Netherlands that consists of new and reused pipelines. The network connects the five Dutch industrial clusters, other countries, hydrogen storage and hydrogen import locations. The operational pressures for the hydrogen network ranges from 30 – 66 bar(g) [6]. HN shared an indicative hydrogen quality and temperature specification on their website, with a minimum hydrogen purity level of 99.5 vol%. There is however still a possibility that Europe will decide to choose a 98 vol% minimum hydrogen purity level due to the inability of repurposed natural gas storages to meet the 99.5% minimum hydrogen purity without purification stages. In this work we will therefore test our findings for an alternative >98 vol% HN specification.

Harbor & rural distribution network

Together with the Expert Assessment group for this project two different networks configurations were defined: a harbor and a rural network. These will be briefly described below.

The harbor network is characterized by a large diversity of industrial end-users including power generation, heating processes, mobility and feedstock (methanol). The network consists of newly built pipelines with relatively short connections. It is expected that given the industrial character of the network, the hydrogen demand pattern will be rather flat (continuous industrial production) with ad hoc spikes due to end users with batch processes. The high volume of hydrogen required by the industry is provided by import and production technologies close by (e.g. electrolyzers, LOHC, hydrogen as by-product and towards 2050 also ammonia and reforming). The harbor network may be connected to HN in 2035 but will certainly have a bi-directional connection with HN by 2050. Figure 2.8 shows a summary of the different producers and end-users connected to the harbor network in 2035 and 2050. The hydrogen purity ranges are indicated by color coding based on the information from the first phase of this work package (see [2] for more details).

Figure 2.8. Harbor network producers and end-users for 2035 (with and without HN connection) and for 2050, mainly using new 16 bar pipelines

The rural/regional network that can be characterized by for example low density population in (small) urban areas. However in the context of the hydrogen purity cost model, “rural” represents “the bidirectional high pressure part of the hydrogen distribution system that contains all market parties that were not connected to harbor networks or to HN directly”. Hydrogen in rural networks will include the main share of the built environment for heating purposes, for personal mobility purposes via distribution hubs, small power generation units (CHP) and several single cluster 6 industries. The network consists mostly of re-used natural gas pipelines with long connections and hydrogen demand will follow a seasonal pattern, with high demand in winter and low demand in summer. Hydrogen will be mainly supplied by electrolyzers (local production) and by 2050 also by means of gasification. These rural networks start as a local stand-alone hydrogen initiative and by 2050 be connected to the HN network. Figure 2.9 shows the hydrogen produces/suppliers and end-users/feed-in connected to the rural network in 2035 and 2050. Information on the hydrogen purity ranges (indicated by color coding) is acquired from the previous phase of this work package [2].

Figure 2.9. Rural network producers and end-users for 2035 and 2050, mostly using exiting (8 bar) pipelines

Road transport fueling stations

Similar to today’s CNG stations, hydrogen fueling stations may be directly connected to the pipeline. In order to meet the strict hydrogen requirements for fuel cell vehicles, either local purification will be required or the hydrogen purity specification for the pipeline will have to meet the stringent requirements (>99.5 vol%). However, as a default, the hydrogen purity model assumes that hydrogen fueling stations will be mainly supplied by local distribution centers and partly via electrolyzers directly by using tube trucks.

2.3.2 Network scopes in hydrogen purity model

In the hydrogen purity model, we select a specific network scope (“Harbor” or “Rural”) and a specific year (2035 / 2050), and the model then first established the capacities of all connected parties and then calculates all the annual purification related costs “lumped together”. In other words, the model calculates “all 2035 Dutch harbor networks” and not for “a typical Dutch harbor network”.

Figure 2.10: possible development stages of a hydrogen network. The model assumed option C is in place, where the interconnection with HN is considered optional.

The hydrogen purity model also assumes that the regional networks are advanced in their maturity (see figure 2.10C), including either active roles of TSO/ DSO in boosting and or gas treating hydrogen as it flows from/ to HN and the regional networks, or operate the regional networks standalone. The model also assumes small subnetworks delivering tail gas from separation stages (“PSA’s”) to local industry aiming to minimize tail gas flaring to an absolute minimum. As for regional network balancing, we assume there will be “smart multifuel industries” switching between natural gas, electric power and hydrogen based on price and electricity/ hydrogen congestion signals.

Figure 2.11 Possible topologies of a hydrogen network. Note that Ring networks can use membranes as a separation technology. We only include option A in this work

In principle there are multiple regional network topologies possible (see figure 2.11), ranging from conventional “tree” type topologies to alternative “ring” topologies (as used in heating networks) or perhaps even “star” networks mostly used in computer networks. Together with the HyDelta 3 WP 1a members it was decided to use a tree topology for this study, but other topologies may be considered in the future. For example, the “ring” topology may be considered in combination with membranes separation technology [2], supplying small scale mobility end-users. When using membranes instead of PSA systems, the tail gas may be “left behind” in the main hydrogen feed, only to be extracted by a central PSA separation stage. This would likely be performed by the DSO at a central location, including a direct connection to a tail gas end user.

When using a “star” topology the DSO would supply each customer with a tailor-made hydrogen specification from a central distribution hub. In other words, highly pure electrolyzer hydrogen would be send to critical customers (mobility, feedstock) and lower grade hydrogen to less discerning customers (refineries). But this type of advanced networks is only considered feasible in a compact area with a limited number of large suppliers and end users (i.e. harbour networks). Moreover, when one connected party falls away, the pipeline would be likely become an “dead asset”.

Given the unconventional nature of “ring” and “star” topologies we only considered conventional “tree” topologies in this work, although the hydrogen purity model is set up to include them in the future.

2.3.3 National scenarios

The starting points for this work are the assumptions on the possible hydrogen market sizes and in particular the category break downs in 2035 and 2050. We used the same dataset as used for the Economic Affairs study in 2023 [3], which are based on the Dutch IP2024 and I13050v2 datasets [7, 8]. The main difference between the scenarios is the overall size of the hydrogen market, including subtle differences in hydrogen sourcing (see *table 2.1*) and end use applications (*table 2.2*). See figure 2.12 for the interrelation of the scenarios. Note that the used EZK 2023 data deviates from the original IP2024 and I13050 studies due to revisions by EZK as a response to the latest 2023 policy updates and market consultations. Moreover, in this study we differentiated and adjusted the EZK data in minor ways to better suite the specific scope of this HyDelta study. This will be discussed in section 2.3.5.

Figure 2.12: national scenarios for 2035 and 2050 and their interrelation. The 2035 KA (Klimaat Ambitie) and 2050 NL (Nationaal Leiderschap) will be used as the default scenarios in this work.

Table 2.1: hydrogen supply as used in this study (source: [3]).

demand (PJ/ year)		2035 scenarios			2050 scenarios			
sector	category	Klimaat Ambitie	Nationale Drijfveren	Internationale Ambitie	Nationaal Leiderschap	Decentrale Initiatieven	Europese Integratie	Internationale Drijfveren
import	maritime	180	56	385	202	182	407	803
industry	byproduct	50	54	43	57	26	45	28
biomass	gasification	5	1	5	5	8	10	11
green hydrogen	electrolysis onshore	52	163	72	263	232	156	93
green hydrogen	electrolysis offshore	32	21	65	228	91	1	91
import	pipeline	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
blue hydrogen	SMR/ ATR +CCS	96	89	89	58	39	201	66
Total		415	384	659	813	578	820	1092

Table 2.2: hydrogen demand as used in the EZK study. Augmentations from the original data indicated in cursives.

demand (PJ/ year)		2035 scenarios			2050 scenarios			
sector	category	Klimaat Ambitie	Nationale Drijfveren	Internationale Ambitie	Nationaal Leiderschap	Decentrale Initiatieven	Europese Integratie	Internationale Drijfveren
fertilizer	feedstock	33	17	35	52	50	35	51
mobility	domestic	28	18	78	36	44	17	115
mobility	maritime	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
mobility	aviation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
power	power plants	26	50	87	135	151	84	124
export	pipelines	161	141	249	135	173	329	471
chem. - industry	feedstock	12	13	12	13	15	19	0
steel	feedstock & heat	8	13	44	47	43	38	11
fertilizer	heat	3	0	2	7	4	15	3
chemical other	feedstock	35	35	36	30	5	22	61
refinery	heat	92	89	89	243	52	163	63
industry other	heat	14	3	12	15	0	0	37
TSO/ DSO	losses	2.5	2.4	4	6	4	4	6
Horti-culture	heat & power	0.44	1.65	6.6	55	22	55	88
Residential	heat	0.09	0.34	1.35	11.25	4.5	11.25	18
heat networks	heat	0.06	0.23	0.9	7.5	3	7.5	12
Agri-culture	heat	0.16	0.6	2.4	20	8	20	32
Commercial	heat	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total (PJ/ y)		415	384	659	813	578	820	1092

The 2035 national scenarios have the following descriptions:

- *Klimaat Ambitie / Climate Ambition*: default scenario based on existing and intended energy & climate policies [9], including additional 2023 ambitions with regards to Hydrogen import and transit to Belgium & Germany.
- *Nationale Drijfveren / National Motives*: Flanking scenario with extra ambitions to accelerate electrification and renewable energy production.
- *Internationale Ambitie / International Ambition*: Flanking scenario with extra focus on renewable gasses like hydrogen and biogas.

The 2050 scenarios have the following descriptions:

- *Nationaal Leiderschap / National Leadership*: default scenario with small reduction industry, strong electrification with focus on solar & wind.
- *Europese integratie / European Integration*: alternative scenario with limited reduction industrial demand and focus on green molecules and CCS.
- *Decentrale Initiatieven/ Decentral Initiatives*: flanking scenario with strong reduction of industrial demand but uptake of hydrogen, strong electrification with focus on solar and wind for the rest of the market
- *Internationale Ambitie: / International Ambition*: flanking scenario with strong reduction of industrial demand, strong focus on hydrogen, including transit and build environment.

All scenarios assume that political targets (i.e. net zero in 2050) will be (just) met. *There are no scenarios where the energy transition was only partially successful.*

2.3.4 Scenario data Mobility sector

For the purposes of this study, we need to split out the national mobility demand data into subcategories (table 2.3) in order to better assign them later to Rural and Harbor networks. To this end we looked up the mobility data using the Quintel ETM web interface [8] :

Table 2.3: mobility data per sector

Demand (PJ/y)		2035			2050		
Category	Klimaat Ambitie	Nationale Drijfveren	Internationale Ambitie	Nationaal Leiderschap	Decentrale Initiatieven	Europese Integratie	Internationale Drijfveren
cars	11.9	9.6	26.5	0.0	0.0	9.6	25.5
trains	0.0	0.0	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
busses	0.3	0.1	2.1	2.2	0.0	2.0	3.2
trucks	15.7	6.1	41.0	24.0	37.5	0.0	66.5
vans	0	1.7	6.3	0.0	0.0	5.7	10.0
barges	0	0.2	0.2	9.8	6.0	0.0	9.8
total	28	18	78	36	44	17	115

We noticed that that the differentiated mobility data in the ETM slightly deviated from the aggregated data used in the EZK study. The reasons for the minor deviations are unclear (no motivation given by EZK in 2023) and we have therefore resorted to the original ETM data again.

Also note that the original mobility data do not include possible hydrogen use for aviation and maritime fuel bunkering. These are out of scope for national energy scenarios and therefore no data was provided for these (very) large end user categories. We however do not expect hydrogen to be used as an aviation fuel or to be provided via a rural or harbor network or hydrogen to be used as ship bunkering fuel even in 2050.

The model also assumes that the main hydrogen mobility technology for 2035 will be fuel cell but towards the future, mainly with hydrogen prices decreasing, also the combustion engine may be reconsidered, especially also for intermittent uses such as earth moving equipment like excavators ([10], [11]). We assume a 90/10 split of fuel cell/ ICE in 2035 and 70/30 split in 2050 for all mobility categories.

2.3.5 Scenario data distribution market

An issue flagged in the original EZK scenario data by the HyDelta team were the large disparities in residential & commercial hydrogen demand between the various scenarios. Basically, only the 2050 *Internationale Ambitie* scenario had any hydrogen demand for the residential & commercial sector, all other scenarios had zero demand. In this study however, we would like to have non-zero values for most of the distribution market categories (agriculture, residential, heat networks, ...). This mainly because the hydrogen distribution market is a primary focus of HyDelta program and 2) zero values in a model input can mask model internal data handling errors. To this end we generated alternative small non-zero values for the residential market using the adoption curves of heat pumps (figure 2.13, a) using the original 2050 *Internationale Ambitie* data. The national scenarios were rebalanced for the new nonzero markets by adjusting the export category.

Figure 2.13: a) adoption curve residential heat pumps (2013-2023) and b) possible adoption curves for hydrogen in the residential sector

By pinning the 2050 *International Ambitie* datapoints to the *fast* curve (figure 2.13b), assuming the 2050 *Nationaal Leiderschap* and *Europese integratie* to be on the *default* curve and *Decentrale initiatieven* on the *slow* curve we could extrapolate all other 2050 and 2035 data as presented in Table 2.2.

2.3.6 Import mix

A key difference between the original scenario, the scenarios updated by EZK in 2023 and assumption in this HyDelta study are on the possible future import mix (table 2.4):

Table 2.4: assumed mix of national hydrogen import sources

	Hydelta3		EZK 2023		original	
	2035	2050	2035	2050	2035	2050
Pipe	0.1	0.1	0	0	1	1
Ammonia	0.5	0.4	1	0.3	0	0
LOHC	0.4	0.4	0	0.3	0	0
Liquid H ₂	0	0.1	0	0.3	0	0

Note that the large differences in views on the future national import mix are of lesser importance as they are primarily connected to HN. However, for harbour networks we do foresee that some large-scale suppliers will also supply the Harbor networks (dual connections), and it is thus of importance that they are represented in the national scenario with annual volume. This explains the differences between EZK and the HyDelta values.

2.3.7 Commodity Prices

In addition to national hydrogen volumes, the hydrogen purity model also requires prices for the main hydrogen commodity, but also for the alternative heat sources, assumed to be natural gas plus carbon emission rights (table 2.5). A key issue with the original price levels is that are from before the 2022 price inflation due to the recent Ukraine crisis. The HyDelta WP 1a members felt that the default 2035 and 2050 hydrogen price expectations need to be hiked by ~50 % to reflect a more fractured future world market with systematically higher European energy prices.

Table 2.5 assumed commodity prices by the techno-economic model

	2035			2050			
	Klimaat Ambitie	Nationale Drijfveren	Internationale Ambitie	Nationaal Leiderschap	Decentrale Initiatieven	Europese Integratie	Internationale Drijfveren
H ₂ (€/kg)	5.3	7.9	3.5	3.8	5.6	3.8	2.5
CO ₂ (€/tonne)	100	100	100	168	168	168	168
Nat. gas (€/MWh)	35	35	35	35	35	35	35

In addition to a default 50% price increase we also applied another 50% hike to the marginal hydrogen scenarios but applied a 50% reduction (i.e. assume original hydrogen prices) to the abundant hydrogen scenarios. This just to have somewhat more scenario differentiation. The CO₂ emission right prices are taken from the ETM model and the natural gas prices reflect the average 2024 TTF price [12]. Note that the original I13050 scenarios assume 15 €/ MWh natural gas prices [8] and these are considered to be less likely given the current geopolitical climate.

2.3.8 Technical assumptions

With the overall national market volumes per category established, the next step is to quantify the impact of these market segments on the harbour and rural hydrogen networks. Based upon the results from previous studies and feedback from the Steering committee we compiled the following lists of key technical parameters (table 2.6 and) [2, 13, 14]:

Table 2.6: key technical assumption for hydrogen production. Suppliers in grey are primarily connected to HN.

Category	Scope	Technology	Ann. Op. Hours (h)	Size (MW)	H ₂ Purity (%) (margin)	Tail gas (0-1) (margin)
import	large scale	NH ₃	5000	1000	95 (+/- 0)	1.0 (+/- 0)
import	large scale	LOHC	6000	1000	99.8(+/- 0.1)	1.0 (+/- 0)
import	large scale	LH ₂	6000	1000	99.99 (+/- 0)	1.0 (+/- 0)
import	large scale	pipe	4000	1000	99.5 (+/- 0)	0.3 (+/- 0.2)
power-2-gas	on shore	electrolyzer	3000	10	99.99 (+/- 0)	0 (+/- 0)
power-2-gas	offshore	electrolyzer	4000	1000	99.9 (+/- 0)	0 (+/- 0)
Blue H₂	large scale	ATR +CCS	8000	1000	96 (+/- 1)	1 (+/- 0)
Blue H₂	large scale	SMR+CCS	8000	1000	96 (+/- 1)	1 (+/- 0)
Blue H₂	large scale	pyrolysis	8000	100	95 (+/- 0)	1 (+/- 0)
biomass+CCS	large scale	pyrolysis	8000	100	95 (+/- 0)	0.95 (+/- 0.05)
biomass	small scale	Gasification	8000	10	95 (+/- 0)	0.95(+/- 0.05)
by product	large scale	various	8000	100	99.7 (+/- 0.2)	0.9 (+/- 0.1)
by product	small scale	various	8000	10	99.7 (+/- 0.2)	0.9 (+/- 0.1)
tube container	small scale	cylinders	3000	1	99.99 (+/- 0)	0.25 (+/- 0.25)
import HN	large scale	Flow reducer	4000	100	99.5 /98	0.7 (+/- 0.2)

Table 2.7: list of key technical parameters (including uncertainty range) in minimum hydrogen purity specification and possibility to utilize tail gas as a local heat source (0= no application, 1= full application). End users listed in grey are assumed to be largely connected to HN and maritime and aviation sectors are out of scope. Avg. size refers to the estimated average capacity per end user site.

Category	Application	Technology	Annual oper. hours (H)	AVG. Size (MW)	H ₂ purity (%)	Tail gas (0-1)
fertilizer	feedstock	reactant	6000	900	99.05 (+/- 0.5)	0.9(+/-0.1)
fertilizer	heat	direct firing	6000	100	97.75 (+/- 0.75)	0.9 (+/-0.1)
steel	feedstock	Red. agent	6000	900	99.25 (+/- 0.25)	0.95(+/-0.05)
steel	heat	direct firing	6000	100	97.75(+/- 0.75)	0.95(+/-0.05)
refinery	feedstock	reactant	6000	900	98.25 (+/- 0.75)	0.95 (+/-0.05)
refinery	heat	direct firing	6000	100	97.75 (+/- 0.75)	0.95 (+/-0.05)
chemicals	feedstock	reactant	6000	270	98 (+/- 1.5)	0.9 (+/-0.1)
chemicals	heat	direct firing	6000	30	97.75 (+/- 0.75)	0.9 (+/-0.1)
other	heat	direct firing	6000	10	97.75 (+/- 0.75)	0.85 (+/-0.15)
other	heat	boiler	6000	10	97.75 (+/- 0.75)	0.85 (+/-0.15)
large scale	power plant	CC-GT	3000	1000	98.25(+/- 0.25)	0.38 (+/-0.13)
small scale	CHP	engine	3000	1	98.25 (+/- 0.25)	0.38 (+/-0.13)
small scale	various	fuel cell	3000	1	99.99 (+/- 0)	0.38 (+/-0.13)
automotive	fuel cell	fuel cell	4000	10	99.97 (+/- 0.02)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
automotive	engine	engine	4000	1	98.25 (+/- 0.25)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
truck	fuel cell	fuel cell	4000	10	99.97 (+/- 0.02)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
truck	engine	engine	4000	1	98.25 (+/- 0.25)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
maritime	fuel cell	fuel cell	4000	10	99.97 (+/- 0.02)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
maritime	engine	engine	4000	1	98.25 (+/- 0.25)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
barge	fuel cell	fuel cell	4000	10	99.97 (+/- 0.02)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
barge	engine	engine	4000	1	98.25 (+/- 0.25)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
agriculture	fuel cell	fuel cell	4000	10	99.97 (+/- 0.02)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
agriculture	engine	engine	4000	0.1	98.25 (+/- 0.25)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
construction	fuel cell	fuel cell	4000	0.1	99.97 (+/- 0.02)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
construction	engine	engine	4000	0.1	98.25 (+/- 0.25)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
aviation	turbine	turbine	4000	1000	98.5 (+/- 0.5)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
aviation	fuel cell	fuel cell	4000	100	99.97 (+/- 0.02)	0.5 (+/-0.5)
residential	heat	boiler	2000	10	98 (+/- 0)	0.75 (+/-0.25)
CHP	Heat/power	fuel cell	2000	1	99.97 (+/- 0.02)	0.75 (+/-0.25)
Heat network	Heat/power	engine	2000	10	98.25 (+/- 0.25)	0.75 (+/-0.25)

The most important assumptions in the list of technical parameters are:

- The annual full load hours are used to calculate the capacity of the end use connections, and the CAPEX of the hydrogen purification stages
- We assumed that the full load hours for future industrial hydrogen application will be somewhat lower than currently used for natural gas as industries will need to become more flexible end users, assisting in ad hoc network balancing and hydrogen price stabilization.

- The full load hours for mobility primarily refer to the regional distribution hubs filling the tube trailers that in turn will supply the filling stations, not to the actual full load hours of cars, trucks.
- The average size (MW) parameter is used to calculate the total number of distinct production or end user sites in regional Harbor networks.
- Note that large scale suppliers and end users will be primarily located in the HN network and will thus not impact the result for Harbort and Rural network. We do assume some smaller scale chemical feedstocks (methanol, peroxide,...) to be connected to regional networks. It is also feasible that a refinery or fertilizer plant will also have a (small) connection to a regional hydrogen network to assist the DSO in network balancing.
- The uncertainty range for producer and end user purity specifications and tail gas application will be tested using optimistic and pessimistic variants.

2.3.9 Hydrogen Separation technologies

In this work we assume that for all connected parties Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) is the separation technology of choice for removing impurities from the hydrogen feed. Membrane technologies are considered only for small scale applications and for “ring topologies”, although we do list the anticipated KPI’s on cost and performance as a comparison. The key difference however is that PSA systems split the hydrogen feed typically into a ~90% filtered hydrogen stream and a ~10 % low pressure stream including all impurities, the “tail gas”. Membranes extract a filtered hydrogen stream from a main hydrogen supply, and therefore increase the impurity levels in the main hydrogen supply, which in turn needs to be purified again at a central location using a PSA system. Membranes thus require an unconventional “ring” type network topology as described in figure 2.11 and are therefore considered out of scope in this work.

Table 2.8: KPI’s for Pressure Swing Adsorption and Membrane hydrogen separation technologies.

	Pressure Swing Adsorption	Membrane
Capex fixed (MEuro)	0.9	0.1
Capex variable (euro/kg H ₂ /h)	244	100
OPEX (%/CAPEX/y)	5	0.5
Recovery (<99.7% / >99.7%)	0.88/0.85	0.90/0.70
Lifetime (y)	25	5

It is also important to note that the model explicitly includes economy of scale considerations. In other words, one large PSA system located at a large production site will be more economically viable than a multitude of smaller units placed at small scale end users. To capture this effect we used the “unit capacity” value to estimate the number of market players and the PSA CAPEX includes a fixed CAPEX offset per PSA installation (€/site) plus a variable capacity cost factor (€/ kg/hour). See figure 2.14 to illustrate the PSA cost curve values.

Figure 2.14 :cost curve for PSA systems [15].

2.3.10 Market splits

With the general market data and technical parameters established, the next step is to distribute the market players across the network scope, being either HN, harbour, rural networks. See table 2.9 and

table 2.10 on the assumptions made in this work. Note that market fractions for HN (year)+Harbor(year)+Rural(year) add up to 1 for year=2035 and year=2050.

Table 2.9: fractional market splits of producer categories over the network scopes (2035/2050).

Category/ year	HN	Harbor	Rural
	2035/2050	2035/2050	2035/2050
Import NH ₃ / liquid/pipe	1/1	0/0	0/0
Import LOHC*	0.8/0.5	0.2/0.5	0/0
Electrolyser onshore*	0.1/0.1	0.2/0.2	0.7/0.7
Electrolyser offshore	1/1	0/0	0/0
Blue H ₂	1/0.7	0/0.3	0/0
Biomass gasification +CCS	1	0	0
Biomass gasification	0/0	1/0.3	0/0.7
Byproduct large scale	0.9/0.9	0.1/0.1	0/0
Byproduct small scale	0.5/0.4	0.5/0.5	0/0.1

*= default balancing supplier

Table 2.10: fractional market splits of end user categories over the network scopes (2035/2050).

Category	HN	Harbor	Rural
	2035/2050	2035/2050	2035/2050
Industry: fertilizer, steel, refinery	1/1	0/0	0/0
Industry: chemicals	0.5/0.5	0.5/0.5	0/0
Industry: other (heat)*	0.4/0.4	0.3/0.3	0.3/0.3
Power (CC-GT)	1/1	0/0	0/0
Power CHP / engine	0/0	0.1/0.1	0.9/0.9
Power fuel cell	0/0	0.5/0.5	0.5/0.5
Mobility Automotive	0/0	0.2/0.2	0.8/0.8
Mobility trucks	0/0	0.2/0.2	0.8/0.8
residential	0/0	0.1/0.1	0.9/0.9

*= default balancing off taker

There is a significant uncertainty on how the market segments will eventually be distributed over the HN, Harbour and Rural networks. The tables indicate our estimates for the default values, but we will apply special “market split variants” in the sensitivity analysis, with a particular focus on exploring supply-demand combinations with the highest impact on hydrogen purification costs. See figure 2.15 on how these limiting market split variants are constructed.

Limit scenarios	“clean” Supply	“dirty” Supply
“clean” consumption	Boost “clean” & Reduce “dirty” supplies & Boost “clean” & reduce “dirty” demand	“Boost “dirty” & Reduce “clean” supplies & Boost “clean” & “reduce” dirty demand
“dirty” consumption	“Boost “clean” & Reduce “dirty” supplies & Boost “dirty” / reduce “clean” demand	“Boost “dirty” & Reduce “clean” supplies & Boost “dirty” & reduce “clean” demand

Figure 2.15: alternative market splits covering extreme combinations of extra “clean/ dirty” supply and /or demand variants.

A “clean supply” variant in a harbour or rural network implies that the relative share of annual electrolyzers production will increase with 30% and the share of hydrogen from biomass gasification will be reduced by 30%. Similarly, “clean demand” implies increasing the mobility share with 30% and reducing the boiler share with 30%. The choice for 30% is an educated guess, merely to get a sense the model result to the split uncertainties. Note that this will introduce additional supply-demand

imbalances and require the regional network to be connected to HN to facilitate additional imports or exports from the national Hydrogen network.

2.3.11 Hydrogen transport by road or direct connections

A factor of uncertainty for future hydrogen transport scenario's is the issue that a potentially significant amounts of hydrogen may be transported directly from the electrolyzers to the mobility filling stations.

The main arguments **for** the wide use of transport by road via tube trailer are:

- Some electrolyzers or mobility filling stations will not have access to a local hydrogen network, especially in rural networks, in 2035 scenarios with low penetration of hydrogen mobility.
- Some rural electrolyzers and filling stations will be in such close proximity, perhaps even on the same industrial site park, that even direct connections via pipeline are feasible.
- Hydrogen from pipelines will likely require filtering in a distribution hub. Hydrogen from electrolyzers does not require additional impurity filtering, only compression.

Arguments **against** wide use of tube trailer transport are:

- A hydrogen tube trailer can transport ~300 kg of hydrogen, which translates to ~40.000 km of range for hydrogen cars (e.g. Toyota Mirai has a fuel consumption of 130 km/ kg hydrogen [16]). A 30.000 l petrol truck however translates to ~450.000 km of range for petrol cars, assuming 15 km per litre petrol. Hydrogen requires ~10 times more filling trucks than petrol.
- Electrolyzers will likely rely strongly on excess renewable electricity supply, which will both be intermittent and seasonal. Mobility stations however require a constant supply, likely peaking during weekdays and during rush hours. Electrolyzers will likely never be able to securely supply mobility filling stations all year round.
- Hydrogen tube trailers represent a road safety risk (just like petrol trucks) and political and social acceptance for heavy road traffic by hydrogen transport trucks will be low.
- For large distances transport pipelines are eventually much more economical.

Table 2.11: assumed fraction of hydrogen transported by the regional network versus transport by road (1= 100%= all transport via pipeline). Note that "0.7 (70%) mobility and 0.75 (75%) electrolyser values" translates to "25% of electrolyser production went directly to filling stations to meet 30% of mobility demand".

network	market	2035 KA	2035 ND	2035 IA	2050 NL	2050 DI	2050 EI
harbour	Mobility	0.7	0.6	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.8
harbour	electrolyzers	0.75	0.96	0.93	0.87	0.83	0.96
rural	Mobility	0.6	0.4	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.8
rural	electrolyzers	0.63	0.75	0.86	0.93	0.83	0.92

It is important to note that we do foresee that mobility filling stations will likely be exclusively supplied via tube truck but from local hydrogen distribution hubs operated by specialized companies (Linde/Air Products/Air Liquide/Shell/etc....). These hubs will require a PSA, a local tail gas customer and compressor. These mobility distribution hubs in turn are supplied via pipelines, including hydrogen from nearby electrolyzers. In other words, all scenarios include tube trucks, but they are likely to drive much shorter distances than petrol transporting trucks currently do.

For the numbers in table 2.11 we assumed that new to be build and more compact harbour networks will find it easier to connect electrolyzers with mobility filling stations than rural networks, especially in 2035. Default assumption for Harbors is a "estimated" 70% share of hydrogen transport via pipelines from electrolyzers to mobility distribution hubs versus 30% direct transport from electrolyzers to mobility stations. For rural networks we assumed a 60% / 40% default pipeline/ tube truck split. Next, we also assumed that for scenarios with low hydrogen mobility penetration ("2035 Nationale Drijfveren" and "2050 Decentrale Initiatieven") the split will be more even, i.e. 60/40 (Harbor) and 40/

60 (Rural), in 2035. However, we assume that road transport will decrease towards 2050 as the regional networks start to cover the entire Netherlands. Also, these assumptions are speculative and therefore we will test the sensitivity of the model output to these assumptions in chapter 2.5.5.

2.4 Results

In this section we address the main finding of the hydrogen purity model for the Harbor and Rural networks for all 2035 and 2050 scenarios, assuming default values only. These are “tree network”, “2035 Klimaat Ambitie” scenario, “HN connection=yes”, “HN specification=99.5%”, “default market split” and a “neutral parameter bias”.

2.4.1 2035 Harbor results using default assumptions.

In figure 2.16 (a and b) we see the output of the hydrogen purity model for the harbour network using default assumptions only for the 2035 scenario. Figure 2.16a shows the overall market cost normalized per kg transported. Figure 2.16b shows the absolute purification cost split out over the various market segments:

Figure 2.16: model results for the 2035 harbour network using default assumptions. a) overall hydrogen purification cost normalized per kg hydrogen transported, b) absolute purification costs split out over producers (green), end users (blue) and “DSO<-> HN interactions” (red). The dotted lines indicate external factors that will impose upper and lower technical limits to the specification.

Figure 2.16a shows the “hydrogen purification cost per kg” but this value, although perhaps the most intuitive, can however be rather ambiguous in the context of the hydrogen purity model as a significant part of the hydrogen on the market will have been purified twice, both at the producers and end users side or at the HN<-> regional network interface. Normally the “€/kg” cost value refers to the purification cost incurred either by a specific producer or end user, but in this work, we focus on the *total market purification costs per total amount of hydrogen transported by the system*.

For this reason, we will choose for rest of this work to use the less ambiguous direct model output “total annual purification related market costs”, split out over all producers, end uses and TSO/ DSO, to determine the overall market “sweet spot”. We can however validate that at ~0.1 €/kg, the purification costs are indeed a fraction of the commodity costs (~5 euro/kg), and the purification costs will not significantly disrupt the assumptions in the hydrogen supply-demand scenario.

Figure 2.16b shows us the following for the 2035 Harbor network purity specifications:

- **Hydrogen grades below 98%.** At very low hydrogen grades (<98%), almost the entire end user market needs to make investment costs in numerous PSA systems, scattered around the market, and find applications for tail gas. This will especially be challenging for the gas-to-power end users, as they have specific operating window above 98% purity and likely no direct use for the huge amounts of tail gas. The low grades would be highly advantageous for the hydrogen producers, but the affected producers (Ammonia cracking, Blue Hydrogen, biomass gasification) either a) already require PSA systems to meet the 97% standard or B) not expected to deliver volume to the regional networks but only to HN or c) like biomass gasification, not expected to have the volumes to make a market impact. Overall costs for specifications below 98% are thus predicted to (very) high. Also, we expect external considerations like fiscal metering or Wobbe stability to put a lower limit on the hydrogen specification. These are however outside the scope of the model.
- **Hydrogen grades between 98% and 99.5%.** At specifications exceeding 98% up to 99.5% the bulk of the end user markets using boilers and engines are now able to directly use the hydrogen from the network. Also, the envisaged chemical feedstock customers connected to the regional harbour networks (mainly Methanol) are assumed to be less critical in terms of hydrogen purity and do not require purification. The only connected parties requiring hydrogen purification are 1) mobility distribution centres, b) biomass gasification and 3) DSO’s boosting excess supply to HN and somehow needing to find a local customer for the tail gas. However as soon as regional network specifications match those of HN at 99.5%, the DSO/ TSO cost factor falls away.
- **Hydrogen grades between 99.5% and 99.99%.** At hydrogen specifications exceeding 99.7% we expect the industrial byproducts suppliers and then also the LOHC importers to struggle to meet the network specifications, thus significantly increasing the overall hydrogen purification costs. Only at 99.99% specifications, we expect the mobility sector to be able to use the hydrogen from the network directly. This is however only feasible if the newly build network is proven to be able to guarantee these very high hydrogen purities over longer distances and time.
- **Sweet spot** All these factors combined result in a small region in the cost spectrum where the overall market costs are the lowest, the so called “sweet spot”. In this case, the sweet spot is in between the HN specification of 99.5% and the lowest grade that industrial byproducts and LOHC importers are expected to supply (99.7% -99.8%).

2.4.2 2035 Rural results using default assumptions

In figure 2.17 we see the results for the 2035 Rural network, assuming all default assumptions. Based on these inputs, including assumptions on market split. Figure 2.17a indicates that the relative cost for hydrogen purification will be much higher than for Harbor networks, projected to be up to 10% of the commodity costs at ~ 0.6 €/kg. The reason for the cost increase is due to the relative high share of mobility end users in the rural networks and the challenge of the distribution centres to find a local industrial tail gas application. The high additional cost may challenge the assumption that purification costs are low enough to not affect the underlying supply-demand scenario. On the other hand, ~ 0.6 €/kg additional increase in hydrogen cost only translates to an ~ 0.005 €/km extra cost to the personal mobility end user, assuming 130 km/kg fuel economy of the Toyota Mirai, and is thus unlikely to impact the hydrogen mobility market.

Figure 2.17b shows us the following for the 2035 Rural network purity specifications:

- **Hydrogen grades below 98%.** The downside of specifications below 98% is the requirement of small residential and industrial customer groups to purify hydrogen. Moreover, there is in 2035 no upside to specifications below 98% as there are no suppliers expected in the rural networks that would prefer to supply grades below 98%. Hydrogen from biomass is only expected to uptake after 2035.
- **Hydrogen grades between 98% and 99.5%.** The attainable sweet spot for rural networks is expected to cover the range between 98 and 99.5%. The lower limit of the sweet spot is set by industrial and residential boiler uses and the upper limit is set by the import of hydrogen form HN.
- **Hydrogen grades between > 99.5%.** Ideally Rural networks should transport the >99.99% hydrogen from electrolysers directly supply the mobility filling stations. Ideally also the >99.5 vol% hydrogen from HN should be purified to this specification by the DSO. However, we expect that the pipeline system, containing re-used natural gas distribution pipelines, will not be able to transport the 99.99% specification and therefore only the sweet spot between 98% and 99.5% should be considered.

Figure 2.17: model results for the 2035 Rural network using default assumptions. a) overall hydrogen purification cost normalized per kg hydrogen transported, b) absolute purification costs split out over producers (green), end users (blue) and “DSO-> HN interactions” (red). The dotted lines indicate external factors that will impose limits to the specification either to the downside due to calorific content metering and/or Wobbe range considerations and upper limits due to contamination by the pipeline’s inner walls or intrusion of outside gasses or water.

2.4.3 Harbor results for all 2035 and 2050 scenarios

In figure 2.18 we see the impact of the 2035 and 2050 scenarios on the harbour specifications. Here we note that for the results shown in this figure a HN specification of 99.5 vol% H₂ was assumed. The thick black line indicates the default scenario’s, i.e. 2035 *Klimaat Ambitie* (KA) and 2050 *Nationaal Leiderschap* (NL). Figure 2.18 is divided into four parts (from top to bottom):

- Total purification costs (“total”, figure 2.16A & E),
- Purification cost for end-users (“consumption”, figure 2.18B & F),
- Purification cost for producers (“production”, figure 2.18C & G),
- Purification cost associated with HN connection (“HN flex”, figure 2.18D & H).

The largest deviations from the defaults we see for the following alternative scenario’s:

- **Power struggles.** The main difference between all 2035 and 2050 scenarios, both default and alternatives, is the large increase in purification costs in the 95% - 98% region. This difference is nearly all due to the uptake of hydrogen for power production towards 2050 and the expected challenges for power producers to find local economic applications for the tail gas.
- **Nett production networks.** The largest deviation from the default in 2035 is from the alternative *Nationale Drijfveren* (ND) scenario, which assumes low hydrogen demand for industrial and mobility applications but does assume high hydrogen production volumes from electrolysis. This combination results in higher requirement to boost hydrogen from harbour networks to HN. The 2050 *Decentrale initiatieven* (DI) scenarios is similar in nature to the 2035 *Nationale Drijfveren* scenario and therefore faces similar issues in the requirement to boost Hydrogen to HN and thus the additional purification costs between 98%-99.5% region.

Figure 2.18: results Harbor for all 2035 and 2050 scenarios. The black line in figure a is identical to the result shown in Figure 2.16. figures B to D show the relative contributions to the cost curve due to producers, end users and HN <-> DSO interactions (“flex”). Note that the large optical difference between 2035 (figure A) and 2050 (figure E) is due to large increase in costs in the 95%-98% region. ND=Nationale Drijfveren, KA = Klimaat Ambitie (default), IA = Internationale Ambitie, INT = Internationale Drijfveren, DI = Decentrale Initiatieven, EI = Europese Integratie, NL = Nationaal Leiderschap (default).

2.4.4 Rural results for all 2035 and 2050 scenarios

In figure 2.19 we see the impact of the 2035 and 2050 scenarios on the Rural network specifications. Similar to the results discussed in the previous paragraph, a hydrogen specification of 99.5 vol% for HN was assumed. The largest deviations from the default scenarios occur for:

- **Power sector struggles.** In 2035 the *Internationale Ambitie* (IA) scenario foresees more hydrogen for small scale power generation and this sector has a very specific operating window and will find it challenging to find local heat applications for huge amount of tail gas.
- **Nett export networks.** The 2035 *Nationale Drijfveren* (ND) scenario is relatively high on hydrogen production from electrolysis but low on the up take of hydrogen for mobility or residential applications. This combination results in rural hydrogen grids to become net exporters to HN, requiring the purification of hydrogen with rural specification are below the 99.5% HN specification. Towards 2050 nearly all rural purification costs are associated with the end users and in particular the mobility sector and (small scale) power production. The main difference between the scenarios is that if all factors combined, the rural networks is set to become either a net exporters or importers from HN.

Figure 2.19: results Rural networks for all 2035 and 2050 scenarios. The black line in figure a is identical to the result shown in figure 2.17. figures B to D show the relative contributions to the cost curve due to consumers, producers and HN <-> DSO interactions (“flex”). ND=Nationale Drijfveren, KA = Klimaat Ambitie (default), IA = Internationale Ambitie, INT = Internationale Drijfveren, DI = Decentrale Initiatieven, EI = Europese Integratie, NL = Nationaal Leiderschap (default).

2.4.5 Summary Harbor and Rural results for all 2035 and 2050 scenarios

In summary, in this chapter we have seen that the hydrogen purity model indeed produces hydrogen network purity “sweet spots” when weighing the hydrogen purity related costs of producers and end users.

For Harbor networks we see a market sweet spot between 99.5% (HN specification) and 99.7% (industrial byproduct and LOHC producers) for all 2035 and 2050 scenarios. **In 2050 we see a broad sweet spot from 98% to 99.7% for three out of four scenarios** and also a sweet spot appear around >99.9+ vol%, but we assume that this specification will likely be too challenging for the DSO to transport and guarantee to mobility end users. Below 98% the costs rise strongly due to (intermittent) power producers unable to find tail gas applications and above 99.7% cost increase strongly due to LOHC and industrial byproduct producers now requiring PSA systems. Moreover, overall purification related costs are expected to be low (~0.1 €/kg transported) due to mobility sector relatively small and end users being able to find local tail gas applications. Moreover, these findings are similar for all scenarios and towards 2050 it is the power sector that dominates the purification costs below 98%.

For Rural networks we see a much less pronounced and broader sweet spot between 98% and 99,5%, as these networks are dominated by electrolysis (no purification needed) and mobility (always purification needed). Here it is the import from HN that sets a preference for specifications between 98% at the lower limit (residential boilers) and 99.5% (HN) at the upper limit. Towards 2050 it is the (intermittent) power sector that dominates costs below their 98% specification. Uncertainty whether rural networks will import or export to HN pins the sweet spot at HN specification (99.5%). In theory there is a sweet spot around “>99.9+” but this specification will be impossible for the DSO to transport using repurposed natural gas infrastructure.

2.5 Sensitivity analysis

The hydrogen purity cost model has many uncertainties in the underlying assumptions about the future hydrogen market and in this chapter, we will test the sensitivity of the main model results for the following subjects:

- Impact of HN network connection. Does a connection with HN significantly impact the main findings?
- Impact of HN network specification. Does a change in HN specification from >99.5 vol% to >98 vol% significantly impact the main findings?
- Market split. How do the large uncertainties in the future market split between HN, Harbor and rural networks impact the main findings?
- Direct road transport: How do the uncertainties in the relative share of direct road transport between electrolyzers and mobility filling stations impact the main findings?
- Parameter uncertainties. How do the large uncertainties in the key technical parameters impact the main findings?

2.5.1 Impact of Harbor network HN connection

The assumption is that in 2035 most networks will not yet be connected to the national HN system but in 2050 most will be. This raises the question how an HN network connection impacts the “sweet spot” of the Harbor purity specification. In figure 2.20 we show the 2035 results for all scenarios, both with (A-D) and without HN connection (E-G). The main difference between the scenarios is that the harbour networks without HN connection required a fine tuning in the supply-demand market splits, mainly by adjusting LOHC & electrolyser supply to match demand or if this was not possible, by adjusting industrial heat demand assuming multifuel operations (hydrogen or natural gas).

Figure 2.20: model results for Harbor networks, all 2035 scenarios, both with (A-D) and without HN connection (E-G). Note that figure A-D is identical to figure 2.18A-D, but is left in place for visual reference purposes. ND=Nationale Drijfveren, KA = Klimaat Ambitie (default), IA = Internationale Ambitie, INT = Internationale Drijfveren, DI = Decentrale Initiatieven, EI = Europese Integratie, NL = Nationaal Leiderschap (default).

The main impact of removing the HN connection of the harbour networks is that the sweet spot widens to between 98% and 99.7%. In other words, the market limits in a standalone harbour network is set by the boiler, engine and turbine specifications at the lower limit and the industrial byproduct producers at the upper specification limit.

2.5.2 Impact of Rural network HN connection

The next question is how an HN network connection will impact the “sweet spot” of the rural purity specification. In figure 2.21 we show the 2035 results for all scenarios, both with (A-D) and without HN connection (E-G). The main difference between the scenarios is that the rural networks without HN connection now required an appropriate balancing mechanism to fine tune the supply-demand market splits. Here we assumed that rural networks may fall back on small scale liquid organic hydrogen carrier (LOHC) production plants, supplied by river barges, or an multifuel industrial end user, or we adjusted the share of electrolysis directly connected to rural networks versus connected directly to HN or Harbor networks.

The main impact of removing the HN connection is that the sweet spot again widens to between 98% and 99.8% (the balancing LOHC suppliers). In case of the alternative 2035 *Nationale Drijfveren* scenario, a significant share of the electrolysis had to be moved to HN, to create network balance. This explains the large overall drop in costs for this scenario as the purification costs before boosting to HN are now absent.

Figure 2.21: model results for rural networks, all 2035 scenarios, both with (A-D) and without HN connection (E-G). Note that figure A-D is identical to figure 2.19A-D but is left in place for visual reference purposes.

The main impact of removing the HN connection of the rural networks is that the sweet spot widens to between 98% and 99.8%. In other words, the market limits in a standalone network are only limited by boiler specifications at the lower and a possible balancing producer (we assumed a LOHC importer) at the upper limit. In real world, it will likely be the technical limits due to pipeline wall interactions that will set the upper specification limit.

2.5.3 Impact of HN networks specification

Throughout this works we have assumed that the HN specification is likely to be 99.5%. It is however possible that the European network operators decide that 98% specification is to be preferred on national and international levels.

The main findings are:

- Harbor results.** Figure 2.22 shows us that the main impact of an alternative HN 98% specification for 2035 Harbor networks is that the sweet spot widens from 99.5-99.7% to 98-99.7%. This is because Harbor networks are expected to be nett exporters of hydrogen to HN and thus a less critical HN specification results in wider harbour specification. Towards 2050 (figure 2.23) the same trends can be seen but less pronounced, because in the default scenario the volume export from the harbour network to HN is expected to decrease.
- Rural results.** Figure 2.24 displays that for the rural networks, the 2035 “sweet spot” widens when setting HN to 98% specification. This because rural networks are expected to be nett importers from HN and purification costs now need to be made for the entire specifications in the 98-99.9 % range. Towards 2050 (figure 2.25) the sweet spot effectively disappears and all rural hydrogen specification in the 98.5%-99.9% are equally attractive.

Figure 2.22: impact of an HN 98% specification on 2035 Harbor results. A-D: original results with 99.5% HN specification, E-H alternative results with 98% HN specification.

Figure 2.23: impact of an HN 98% specification on 2050 Harbor results. A-D: original results with 99.5% HN specification, E-H alternative results with 98% HN specification.

Figure 2.24: impact of an HN 98% specification on 2035 Rural network results. A-D: original results with 99.5% HN specification, E-H alternative results with 98% HN specification

Figure 2.25: impact of a HN 98% specification on 2050 Rural network results. A-D: original results with 99.5% HN specification, E-H alternative results with 98% HN specification

In conclusion, the main impact of a 98% HN specification versus a 99.5% specification is that the sweet spot now widens to cover the entire 98%-99.7% range (Harbor) and 98-99.9 % range for rural networks, with the true upper specification limits set by technical factors such as pipeline wall contamination.

2.5.4 Impact of market splits

As discussed in chapter 2.4, there is a considerable uncertainty in assigning the various market segments over the HN, Harbor, Rural networks. In order to test the sensitivity of the HN/Harbor/Rural market splits, the model has the built-in option to vary the supply and demand market segments with a “boost” or “reduction” factor. Specifically, we will test for the four (see figure 2.15 in section 2.3.10 : Market splits) challenging situations where either the “clean” (electrolysers) or “dirty” (gasification) suppliers are reduced or boosted and the “clean” end users (mobility) or “dirty” end users (boilers and engines) are reduced or boosted. The main findings as shown in figure 2.26 and figure 2.27 are:

- Harbor networks:** In 2035, the main impact of market split uncertainties is the amount of interaction with the HN network, resulting in larger uncertainty of the costs between 98-99.5% and 99.5-99.99%. Towards 2050, it also affects the costs below 97% due to the large increase in power generation sector. However, as for 2035 and in 2050 these do not affect the main cost trend and the “sweet spot” as shown by the default split.
- Rural networks:** the main impact of market split uncertainties in 2035 is the overall costs associated with mobility end users (figure 2.27). However, as these costs are mainly constant between 95% and 99.99%, this mainly introduces an uncertainty in the y-axis offsets of the default trend. Towards 2050 the main impact of uncertainty is on the hydrogen export to HN. However, as for 2035 and in 2050, these do not affect the main cost trend and the “sweet spot” as shown by the default split.

Figure 2.26: impact of “cleaner” or “dirtier” market split variations on the 2035 (A-D) and 2050 (E-G) Harbor networks compared to the default scenarios.

Figure 2.27: impact of “cleaner” or “dirtier” market split variations on the 2035 (A-D) and 2050 (E-G) Rural networks as compared to the default market split.

In conclusion, uncertainties on the future market split between HN, Harbor and Rural networks do not significantly affect the main findings concerning the location or width of the “sweet spot”, merely the depth of the sweet spot.

2.5.5 Impact of road transport

In addition to uncertainty in the HN/ Harbor/ Rural split of the market categories there is the additional uncertainty of electrolyzers bypassing the networks and directly supplying the filling stations by tube trailer, or possibly supplying mobility stations located directly near electrolyzers. This is discussed in section 2.3.11 including the proposed market split corrections, with considerable uncertainties in the underlying assumptions. In this section we check the impact of the assumptions by running the hydrogen purity model **with** and **without** the road transport correction.

Figure 2.28: impact of the 2035 Harbor results with road transport correction (A-D) and without road transport correction (E-H). The impact is minimal.

Figure 2.28 clearly shows that the impact of direct road transport between electrolyzers and mobility stations is minimal for harbour networks in 2035. This mainly because the relative share of mobility is relatively small for Harbor networks. Not shown is the impact for 2050 Harbor networks as the impact is similarly marginal and hardly discernible by eye.

Figure 2.29 shows that the impact of direct road transport between electrolyzers and mobility stations is much larger for rural networks. This because the relative share of mobility stations is much larger for rural networks than for harbour networks. Without direct road transport between electrolyzers and mobility filling stations, the amount of hydrogen that needs to be purified in mobility distribution centres increases, and thus the amount of tail gas increases. The result is an offset in costs that all hydrogen purities between 95% and 99.9 %. The offset however does not impact the mean and the width of the “sweet spot”. Figure 2.30 shows that these findings do not change significantly towards 2050. Moreover, the relative impact of direct road transport between electrolyzers and mobility stations only decreases due to the much stronger uptake of hydrogen for stationary power generation (engines and fuel cells).

Figure 2.29: impact of the 2035 Rural results **with** road transport correction (A-D) and **without** road transport correction (E-H).

Figure 2.30: impact of the 2050 Rural model results with road transport correction (A-D) and without road transport correction (E-H).

In conclusion, the impact of direct road transport between electrolyzers and mobility stations is marginal for **harbour** networks and mainly results in a small extra cost offset for the **rural** networks. There is no impact on the mean value width and depth of the “sweet spot”.

2.5.6 Impact of parameter uncertainties

The last sensitivity we examined is the intrinsic uncertainty in key technical parameters such as:

- Maximum possible hydrogen specification of the producer categories. Here the main uncertainty are technical capabilities of the LOHC importers, industrial byproduct and biomass gasification in what hydrogen specification they can produce without using a PSA system. Ammonia cracking, blue hydrogen and liquid Hydrogen importers are all assumed to be connected to HN and thus of lesser importance. There is less uncertainty in the ability of the LOHC and gasification producers to find local tail gas applications as the main hydrogen production processes require significant amounts of external heat.
- Minimum required hydrogen specification of the end user categories. There is still some uncertainty in the minimum specification required by smaller industrial feedstock end users, for example methanol and peroxide end users. There is less uncertainty about the minimum specifications of boiler, engines and fuel cells. However, for the power and mobility sector and the TSO/ DSO the key uncertainty lies in the ability of the end users to find local tail gas applications all year round.

All these uncertainties in technical specifications and tail gas application can be summarized in two cases:

- The optimistic case where producers are well capable in producing clean hydrogen, end users are less critical and all market parties, including the TSO/ DSO, have few issues in finding tail gas applications.
- The pessimistic case where all market parties struggle in either producing or using clean hydrogen and finding economic tail gas applications.

In figure 2.31 we see that the main finding for the **harbour** network are that there is a strong impact on the position of the upper (~99.7%) and lower limits (~98%) of the sweet spot due to uncertainties in the exact specifications of the LOHC producer and the industrial end users. There is relatively small impact on the depth of the sweet spot due to sufficient local applications for tail gas. In figure 2.32 we see that for **rural** networks a comparable finding, with similar uncertainty in the lower limit, but no upper limits uncertainty due to the absence of LOHC importers or industrial byproducts. Also, there is now more uncertainty in the depth of the sweet spot due to larger uncertainties in end user ability to find local tail gas applications. However, in both cases the main findings remain unaffected.

In conclusion, for **harbour** networks we see uncertainty in both the upper and lower limit of the sweet spot due to technical abilities of LOHC and non-mobility end users. The depth of the sweet spot is relatively unaffected due to the ability of the market to find tail gas applications. For **rural** networks we only see uncertainty in the lower limit of the sweet spot, set by boiler and power end-users, but relatively more impact on the depth of the sweet spot, due to larger uncertainties of mobility distribution centres to find local tail gas applications all year round.

Figure 2.31: the impact of parameter uncertainty in the optimistic and pessimistic case for the Harbor network in 2035 (A-D) and 2050 (E-H)

Figure 2.32: the impact of parameter uncertainty in the optimistic and pessimistic case for the Rural network in 2035 (A-D) and 2050 (E-H).

2.6 Summary and conclusions

As part of the HyDelta 3 research program, we have performed an in-depth study into the optimal hydrogen purity specifications for future Dutch regional hydrogen distribution networks. We created a techno-economic model, the hydrogen purity cost model, based on a methodology used in a previous study performed for the ministry of Economic Affairs [3, 17]. A techno-economic analysis was performed using the model for two regional network scopes (harbour and rural) including their interactions with the national hydrogen network (HN) and on seven production/consumption scenarios for the years 2035 and 2050. Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) is the key hydrogen purification technology, which produces besides high purity hydrogen also a tail gas stream including the filtered-out impurities. Finding economic applications for tail gas is one of the major hydrogen purification related cost drivers. Note that the model only considers the hydrogen purity related costs from a supplier, end user and HN connection point of view and does not include technical limitations due to hydrogen pipeline wall interactions.

For Harbor networks we see a market sweet spot between 99.5% (HN specification) and 99.7% (industrial byproduct and LOHC producers) for all 2035 and 2050 scenarios. For 2050 three out of four scenarios have a broader sweet spot between 98% and 99.7% as the three scenarios do not foresee large hydrogen volume exchanges with HN, whereas the fourth scenario does foresee large scale boosting to HN. Below 98% the hydrogen purification costs rise strongly due to (intermittent) power producers unable to find tail gas applications and above 99.7% cost increase strongly due to LOHC and industrial byproduct producers now requiring PSA systems. Moreover, overall purification related costs are expected to be low (~0.1 €/kg transported) due to mobility sector relatively small and end users being able to find local tail gas applications. Moreover, these findings are similar for all scenarios and towards 2050 it is the power sector that dominates the purification costs below 98%.

For Rural networks we see a much less pronounced and broader sweet spot, as these networks are dominated by electrolysis (no purification needed) and mobility (always purification needed). These two market players actually create a theoretical “sweet spot” around “99.99%” but transporting this specification via existing infrastructure will be completely infeasible. For the much broader technically feasible sweet spot, it is the residential boilers and the import from HN that sets a preference for specifications between 98% at the lower limit (residential boilers) and 99.5% (import HN) at the upper limit. Towards 2050 it is the (intermittent) power sector that dominates costs below their 98% specification. Uncertainty whether rural networks will import or export to HN pins the sweet spot at HN specification (99.5%). The rural hydrogen purification related costs in the broader 98% -99.5% sweet spot are projected to be significant at an estimated ~0.6 €/kg for the fuel cell mobility sector. However, this additional cost translates to an ~0.005 €/km cost increase for personal mobility end users and is thus unlikely to negatively impact the development of this market segment. Last but not least, we have established the robustness of these main findings for the following market uncertainties:

- Alternative 2023 and 2050 market scenarios
- Regional networks with or without HN connection
- HN specification @ >98% instead of >99.5%
- Large uncertainties in the market split of the various production and end use categories between HN/ Harbor and Rural networks.
- Uncertainties in the role of direct transport from electrolyzer to mobility stations via tube trailers.
- Uncertainties in the underlying technical parameters.

The main finding is that none of these uncertainties will significantly alter any of the key insights.

3. Effect of permeation and desorption on hydrogen quality

Previous chapters gave insight in the economics of hydrogen quality, presenting a techno-economic optimum on hydrogen quality. In this chapter it is modelled how hydrogen purity is affected by transporting it through pipelines. When existing natural gas distribution networks are repurposed for the distribution of hydrogen, contaminants present might have an influence on the hydrogen purity. Contaminants that are potentially present in repurposed distribution pipe lines are:

- natural gas components (THT³, natural gas condensate)
- (mining) dust, soil components or seepage from drill fluids
- components from the environment (oxygen, nitrogen and water)

The gas quality is determined based on the components present in the gaseous phase. Mining dust, other dust and solid components from soil and drill fluids are solid components and as such have no influence on the hydrogen purity. Natural gas components (THT, aromatics and alkanes) are absorbed into the pipe wall and will desorb from the wall into the transported hydrogen gas, reducing the hydrogen purity. Pollutants from the environment (nitrogen, oxygen and water) entering the pipes, through the inevitable process of permeation will, also negatively affect the purity of the transported hydrogen gas. Therefore this study focusses on the physical phenomena, permeation from components from the environment and desorption of natural gas components. Other factors that can alter hydrogen gas quality such as ingress during construction or maintenance activities, or through cracks or fractures due to incidents are not included in this research. Ingress of oxygen and nitrogen through small fractures is not expected to occur, given the overpressure that prevails in the gas network. In the event of an incident such as a pipe burst due to excavation works or due to failure of an adjacent water pipeline, the pipe segment in question will be repaired and put into service according to established regulation procedures. The influence of water seeping into cracks on the hydrogen purity has not been investigated, but is of influence just as it is for natural gas. During normal operation permeation continuously affects the hydrogen purity, whereas the effects of adsorption are limited only to the beginning of the operational lifecycle. The following subchapters therefore focus on these two phenomena.

3.1 Permeation has an effect on the gas quality

This part of work package 1A focusses on the influence of permeation on gas quality. Permeation is a naturally occurring process where a gas, fluid or vapor “moves” through a solid barrier layer (like a pipeline wall). This process is driven by a difference in concentration across this barrier, the gases want to permeate through this barrier. This process takes place in two directions: pressurized gas permeates to the environment, and components from the environment (nitrogen and oxygen present in air and water present in the soil) permeate through pipe wall into the (gaseous) flow. When transporting hydrogen, the gases that permeate into the hydrogen flow affect the hydrogen quality. Gas quality is one of the parameters in a hydrogen network that is important for producers, customers and network operators. Therefore, the permeation in such a network was modelled.

Permeation is influenced by multiple factors: the material, the permeate and environmental circumstances. For example, the type of material used, the dimensions of the pipe, gas composition, temperature and partial pressure differences. Metallic materials are generally more resistant to permeation compared to plastic materials. Steel materials have a hydrogen permeability coefficient that is one to two orders of magnitude lower than those of plastic pipes [18]. Therefore, steel pipes

³ In line with previous reporting, THT is referred to as a natural gas component, because this substance -although not naturally present natural gas- is inextricably linked to natural gas and the distribution grid and in ISO 6976 as is included as such.

were not included in this study, but only PE and PVC⁴ pipes were considered as they represent the worst-case scenario.

Another important parameter influencing the gas quality is the residence time of the gases inside and outside the pipe network. It is assumed that the pipe is completely surrounded by air on the outside. The environment (soil) is well ventilated. Therefore, there is no change in concentrations of gases in air. The effects of any capillary water, cracks, and obstacles in the soil are excluded, as well as influence of soil types, soil stratification, and soil homogeneity. The residence time inside the pipe is determined by the flow rate of the gas, which is therefore of great influence on the permeation process. Because this work package focusses on gas quality reasons only the gasses entering the pipe are modeled, gasses permeating outwards are not included.

3.2 The amount of permeation was calculated in a model

To provide insight into the influence of these parameters on hydrogen distributed through an gas network, a spreadsheet model has been created containing various parameters as illustrated in figure 3.1.

Adjustable parameters			
Urban	Rural		
Continuous flow	Batch flow		
Selectable flow time from entry to customer			
Used for network configuration		Taken from literature	
Average SDR per material and pressure		Permeation coefficients of:	
Average diameter of pipe network per material and pressure		PE	PVC
Average length of pipeline network per material and pressure		For:	
Six different pressure (8, 4, 3, 1, 0.1, 0.03 bar)		Nitrogen	Hydrogen Water

Figure 3.1. Parameters using the permeation model.

Ultimately, this results in 78 different permeation calculations that together calculate the total contamination for different scenarios at the customers. Here a hydrogen quality of 100 vol% is assumed as entry quality.

The model calculations are performed for two networks: an urban and a rural network. In both cases the network starts with high pressure pipelines (8 bar) followed by lower pressure pipelines until the lowest pressure is reached. In the rural network, the lowest pressure is 100 mbar, in the urban network the grid is split up in two sections; a 30-mbar grid and a 100mbar grid, both fed by the same length of high pressure pipeline. In the rural network the average pipe length is 32 meters per connection (including steel piping material), while in urban network this is 10 meters (at 100 mbar) and 11 meters (at 30 mbar). This is as expected; In a rural network, the distances between connections are larger than in an urban network. The networks are modelled on two real networks. Each net would give slightly different values, but in order to be able to calculate some realistic scenarios, two networks were modelled.

The urban grid is divided into two parts: up to and including the 1 bar the networks are the same, after which it can be split into a 100-mbar sub grid and a 30 mbar sub grid.

⁴ PE = polyethylene and PVC = polyvinylchloride

Figure 3.2. The average pipe length per connection in the urban network (left) and in the rural network (right)

As far as flow through the grid is concerned, the duration in which the gas flows from entry point to exit point is freely adjustable. For the "summer holiday" scenario, 14 days is assumed, while in a winter scenario, 0.01 days is assumed. The flow can be modelled in two ways.

1. **Batch flow.** In this case, there is no gas demand and the gas remains stagnant in the network. After the elapsed time, the entire gas volume goes to the end user as 1 batch.
2. **Continuous flow.** In this situation it is assumed that a volume takes a specified time to flow from entry point to the exit point. So, there will be a small volume of gas flowing through the piping system continuously. In the rural network 14 day-scenario, the flow rate through the pipeline is about 0.9 l/h.

The "continuous flow" calculation has a lower pollution due to permeation in the same time span than the "batch flow". This is because in the "continuous flow" scenario, new (uncontaminated) gas flows into the pipeline during the entire period, resulting in a larger total amount of gas over which the amount of permeated gas is distributed.

3.3 Boundary conditions of the model

The actual temperature and temperature fluctuations of the pipe in the grid are not included in the calculations. The permeability coefficients resulting from permeation tests on which the model was based were performed at 20°C [18]]. For other temperatures there are too few permeation factors available. However, a lower temperature results in a lower molecular mobility of gases and polymer chains with a lower permeation rate as a consequence. Since the average ground temperature in the Netherlands is around 11°C, the calculated volume of permeation is higher than what is expected in reality.

As the contamination increases, the partial pressure difference⁵ will decrease. This is not included in the model, so for higher amounts of pollution, an error is introduced which would lead to an overestimation of pollutants. However, the deviations in the calculations for this work package will be limited as the degree of contamination remains <1%.

The contamination is averaged over all customers. In reality customers who are at the end of the network will receive gas with more contamination than customers who are close to the entry point. However, the actual degree of contamination is also highly dependent on the net topology and the amount of offtake.

⁵ Partial pressure difference is the difference in partial pressure of a gas on both sides of the barrier layer (tube wall)

3.4 The amount of impurities and effect on gas quality can be calculated in the model

If the winter scenario is taken into account, the contamination caused by permeation is close to zero. In winter, the amount of clean hydrogen entering the pipeline is very large compared to the amount of gases that permeate through the pipeline, giving a big dilution effect. This is different for the summer scenario; In the batch flow case where there is no gas flow for 14 days, there will be a significant amount of contaminants, as shown in table 3.1. The table shows the individual of contaminants as well as the total influence of the contaminants on the hydrogen purity.

Table 3.1. Results for summer scenario (batch flow – no gas flow for 14 days)

Species (batch flow)	Rural	Urban 100 mbar	Urban 30 mbar
O ₂ [ppm]	812	58	73
N ₂ [ppm]	2143	109	121
H ₂ O [ppm]	367	13	12
Total contamination [ppm]	3322	180	206
Hydrogen quality [%]*	99,67	99,98	99,98

***Assuming hydrogen infeed with 100% purity**

Table 3.1 shows the results of calculating the summer scenario expressed in parts per million (ppm) level. The rural network has more pollution than the urban network. This can be explained by the pipe length and pipe material. In the case of the rural network, the gas quality would change in 14 days from 100% at entry point to 99.67% at the customers end.

Table 3.2. Results for summer scenario (continuous flow)

Species (continuous flow)	Rural	Urban 100 mbar	Urban 30 mbar
O ₂ [ppm]	316	17	20
N ₂ [ppm]	1079	57	52
H ₂ O [ppm]	214	11	9
Total contamination [ppm]	1609	85	81
Hydrogen quality [%]*	99,84	99,99	99,99

***Assuming hydrogen infeed with 100% purity**

Also in the continuous flow calculations, there is more contamination in the rural network than in the urban network (table 3.2). However, the total contamination is about half compared to the values shown in table 3.1, which is the result of the larger volume of gas flowing through the grid in the 14 days.

It is also possible to calculate the maximum residence time of the hydrogen gas in order to guarantee a certain quality. This is based on the worst-case scenario, i.e. the batch flow rural scenario. To guarantee a hydrogen purity of 99.9 vol% (starting with a hydrogen purity of 100%), the gas can reside in the network for a maximum of 4 days and 5 hours. **For a hydrogen purity of 99.5% this is about 21 days, and for a hydrogen purity of 99.0% it is about 42 days.**

3.5 Impurities contribution of different pipeline sections

Figure 3.3 shows the relative contribution to contamination of different pipeline sections to the contamination of oxygen, nitrogen and water in the rural network.

Figure 3.3. The relative contribution of pipe sections per pressure and material in the rural network.

The results from figure 3.3 can be compared with figure 3.2. Operating at high pressures results in a very small contribution in terms of length and contribution. For nitrogen, the distribution is somewhat similar to the distribution in figure 3.2. For oxygen, the PE part is relatively large in relation to the length. As far as water is concerned, only PVC has a contribution. This is due to the permeability coefficients of the different materials with respect to water. Water can permeate more easily through PVC than through PE, so the relative share of PVC is greater [19].

Permeation rates of gasses from the environment into the pipe is independent of the operational pressure in the pipe. However, the model shows that at high pressures, the amount of permeated contamination has a lower influence. This can be explained by the fact that high-pressure gas is generally transported through pipes with a thicker wall thickness, meaning less contamination enters the pipeline. In addition, at high pressure, there are more normal cubic meters of gas in a pipeline with the same diameter/length. As a result, there is more gas present with which the permeated contaminants are mixed. At higher pressures, there is therefore less incoming contamination (due to the greater wall thickness) and more gas (due to the higher pressure) in which it mixes. The result of this is that permeation has a much more limited role in the high-pressure pipes. For a 100 mm diameter pipeline of PE the contents of the 8 bar (SDR11) line takes 20 times as long to reach the same percentage of impurities as a 100mbar (SDR26) pipeline.

3.6 Effect of desorption in repurposed natural gas lines on hydrogen gas quality

When a pipeline had been used for natural gas transport prior to transporting hydrogen, (trace) components of natural gas are absorbed into the pipe wall. These components slowly desorb from the pipe wall when there is no more natural gas present inside the pipe. If the pipe is filled with hydrogen, the gas quality of the hydrogen is affected by this desorption process. This paragraph will answer the questions that arise: How much will be desorbed? In which timeframe will this occur? What are the consequences of this process?

The desorption process of repurposed pipelines was investigated in HyDelta 1 WP1C [19]. It should be noted that newly installed pipelines also desorb materials into the hydrogen stream, however this was not investigated in this work package. This phenomenon could be further investigated if new pipelines are to be used with high hydrogen quality standards.

For modeling the rate of desorption of natural gas components (including THT) the Elovich formula is used:

$$\frac{dQ_t}{dt} = \alpha \cdot e^{\beta \cdot Q_t} \quad (3.1)$$

Here Q_t is the amount of desorbed natural gas component (mass based) and α and β are material and quantity specific indicators. To determine the values of these specific indicators, tests using pipe segments filled with hydrogen have been performed. The results can be seen in figure 3.4, figure 3.5 and figure 3.6. Here the desorption of alkanes, aromatics and THT as a function of time was measured. At each measurement point, the sample gas was analyzed and new hydrogen was injected into the test sample. The first measurement was performed after the gas was in the pipe segment for 2 days. In the last measurement step the gas was contained for 22 days. Most materials reached a saturation point after 27 days.

3.7 Desorption in real-world practice

From the tests it is evident that the phenomenon of desorption is only an issue in the first days of operation. If a repurposed hydrogen pipeline is in use for more than 50 days, the desorption of components becomes very low. Particularly if hydrogen is flowing through a pipe the concentrations accumulating in the gas are small.

One could argue that desorption could pose a problem at the start of a repurposing project. In this case main lines can be filled with hydrogen, and as users typically get connected at a later stage, the hydrogen can be in a no-flow situation for several days or weeks. To develop a line of reasoning for this worst-case scenario we can use the highest amounts of desorbed natural gas components that were measured. In the beginning of the tests the hydrogen was contained in the pipeline for 2 days. If the results of the alkanes and the aromatics from the two worst scoring pipe segments are summed up, a concentration of 750 ppm of contaminants is found. This corresponds to 0.075 vol%. If this is compared to the proposed Hynetwork hydrogen quality of 99.5 vol% with a tolerance of 5000 ppm sum of total hydrocarbons, it can be reasoned that even in this worst-case scenario, desorption is only a negligible amount. However, if the exit specification cannot be met, a relatively simple solution is available; just before the first customer starts utilizing the connection, flare the hydrogen that is present in the pipeline. This will be beneficial in two ways:

1. The gas that was present absorbed most of the contaminants. The pipeline after flushing is therefore less contaminated. So even if there is still a period of standstill of the newly fed in hydrogen, less contaminants will be absorbed into this gas.
2. The newly fed in gas will have significantly less contaminants, therefore the first user has purer gas to start with. Once offtake is taking place, the fact that there is flow greatly reduces the amount of contaminants that enter the hydrogen per volume.

One of the parameters to judge whether or not hydrogen should be flared depends on the usage of the first customer. Usually, hydrogen combustion processes can easily operate with these low amount of extra hydrocarbons. Feedstock and fuel cell processes might be more sensitive. Consulting with the customer is key on this decision.

3.8 The desorption influence of THT

Tetrahydro thiophene (THT) is an organic sulfur compound used as an odorant in natural gas in the Netherlands. In the recent Dutch hydrogen pilot projects the same odorant is used, as is used for natural gas. There is still uncertainty around odorization and the usage of THT. There are two possible scenarios; the first is that THT is used for hydrogen networks in the same concentration as it

was used with natural gas operation. In this case, the desorption of THT is not an issue. It actually is beneficial to use repurposed pipelines, as new pipelines absorb THT, leading to a decrease in odorant. The second scenario is that no, or a different, odorant is used. In this case THT is desorbed into the THT-free hydrogen. Figure 3.6 gives an indication of the rate at which this occurs. The maximum value found is 36 mg/m³. Using the ideal gas law it can be calculated that this corresponds to 10 ppm (see also Appendix B). Again, percentage wise this has no significant influence on the overall gas quality. It should be noted that the maximum allowable sum of all sulfur components according to the indicative HN gas quality specification is only 3 ppm [6]. However, this is for the unodorized hydrogen in the transport grid. Another point to take into account is that THT has a lower odor threshold of 3.6 mg/m³ [20]. As can be seen in figure 3.6 that after 50 days, a value of 5 mg/m³ can still be measured, this could be one of the concerns.

One of the possible problems with THT is that fuel cells are susceptible for contaminants, especially sulfur. A small literature survey indicates that inside the fuel cell THT is transformed into H₂S, which is one of the important molecules that degrades fuel cells [21]. This transformation takes place with a maximum factor of 0.4 (so 5 ppm THT becomes max 2 ppm H₂S). The most susceptible fuel cells have a limit of <0.1 ppm H₂S [21]. This means a maximum amount of 0.25 ppm of THT (~0.9 mg/m³) should not be exceeded in the feedstock hydrogen. This amount can easily be obtained with desorption of repurposed lines. Therefore, further investigation is required on the influence of THT traces on fuel cells, and on the amount of time that repurposed pipeline desorbs THT at levels that are negative for fuel cells.

Figure 3.4: Desorption of alkanes into hydrogen (from [19]).

Figure 3.5: Desorption of aromatics into hydrogen (from [19]).

Figure 3.6: Desorption of THT into hydrogen (from [19]).

3.9 Conclusions on permeation and desorption

In this chapter the results of a theoretical study into the influence of permeation and desorption on gas quality inside a grid are described. Both phenomena have an impact on the gas quality that is supplied to the end-user. For permeation, a model is developed that is used to provide insight into this influence by means of two different networks (rural/urban) and two scenarios (winter/summer). Depending on the net topology and consumption, it can be calculated if a certain quality may or may not be guaranteed. For desorption previous work was further projected on the effects on repurposed natural gas grids used for hydrogen.

The results show that in periods with high offtake (comparable with the current natural gas offtake in winter), permeation and desorption do not have a significant effect on gas quality. However, when there is (almost) no flow (comparable with the current natural gas offtake in summer), permeation and desorption can lead to a significant amount of impurities in the hydrogen flow. The difference is that desorption only takes place in the beginning of hydrogen transport through the pipeline, whereas permeation can pose a problem in the entire lifecycle.

Desorption will only be an issue in the first days of operation, except for THT, this will desorb from the pipeline for a longer period of time. Especially if fuel cells are connected, problems could arise due to the sulfur component in THT. This should be further investigated if such a user case should present itself.

For permeation, the main conclusion is that hydrogen quality will be reduced during pipeline transport by permeation of nitrogen, oxygen and water from the environment into the gas grid.

Generally speaking, at higher operating pressures both the material thickness and the volume of hydrogen to which impurities dissolve increases. If, for example, 100% pure hydrogen enters the distribution grid the hydrogen quality sweet spot of 99.5% can be guaranteed for the high pressure distribution grid as long as there is continuous flow and no exceptional situations. However during a longer period of no offtake the influence of permeation is more evident, especially in the low pressure section of the grid. In the case of the modelled rural network, the gas quality would change in 14 days from 100% at entry point to 99.67-99.84% at the end user, depending on the model used. This is a quality reduction of 0.33-0.16%. This is only in the modelled case, but it indicates that the sweet spot of 99.5% might not be guaranteed in lower pressure distribution grids with certain net configurations. Specifications in between 98-99.5% with higher allowed impurities for nitrogen, oxygen and water could be proposed in these cases.

There is currently no ministerial regulation for hydrogen. A first exploration into hydrogen specifications of entry and exit points for the distribution network was conducted in 2021 [22]. These specifications are intended as an starting point to collectively reach national regulatory framework. The results of this research can be used as additional information to arrive at attainable regulation. For future ministerial regulation, a number of options can be devised to guarantee different gas qualities for different purposes. For example, customers connected to the 100-mbar network would be supplied with a lower quality than to connected parties to an 8 or 16 bar pipeline. Another option is to not guarantee gas quality 100% of the time. For example, in the summer months, a lower gas quality would be offered for a number of hours/days than in the winter months.

To increase the results of the model, new permeation measurements should be performed to include temperature. Additionally, the model could be added to grid-calculation software to better determine the expected contamination from permeation in a (to be) realized grid. This would also allow to incorporate different residence times of the hydrogen gas based on different consumers. The hydrogen demand for industrial off takers will be more stable and continuous throughout the year. Whereas the hydrogen distributed to the build environment for heating will experience winter and summer influences comparable to those for natural gas. The results in this study are based on historical consumption. In the future, distribution grids can also be used for bi-directional hydrogen transport. Relatively small amounts of hydrogen can be fed into the grid at various locations, after which they have to be transported to the gas storage. Especially on sunny/windy days, this could become an option. In that case, it is necessary to re-examine the impact permeation can have on gas quality as bi-direction flow was not included here.

4. Hydrogen quality management in future distribution grid

In chapter 2 and 3 of this report the result of research activities on the hydrogen purity level in distribution networks has been presented. A market techno-economic and infrastructure technical material track have been presented. Combining both results will unveil a first concept of managing future hydrogen networks.

Figure 4.1 Bringing together input from market techno economic and infrastructural track

For the **market techno-economic analysis** of the optimal hydrogen purity level in regional gas distribution networks, a hydrogen purity cost model was developed. The model give insight in the optimal purity specification (sweet spot) of hydrogen in the regional transmission networks from societal view based on existing market scenarios about the development of the hydrogen market. A harbour and a rural network have been modelled to understand the optimal hydrogen purity level.

Case 1: Harbor hydrogen network:

8-16 bar, large diversity of high density industrial demand (including power generation, heating processes, mobility and feedstock (methanol)) - network consist of newly built steel pipelines with relatively short connections
The hydrogen demand pattern is rather flat (continuous industrial production) with ad hoc spikes due to end users with batch processes.

From the techno-economic market modelling result we can conclude that for the **harbour network** case study, the market sweet spot is between 99.5% and 99.7% for all 2035 and 2050 scenarios. The main drivers for this sweet spot are; a) there will be considerable industrial feed stock demand with a strong preference for hydrogen specifications >99.5% , b) the bulk of the hydrogen producers will either not be able to meet even a

98% specification without purification (Ammonia import, blue hydrogen) or easily meet the 99.7% specification (electrolyzers, LOHC import, liquid Hydrogen imports) and c) the harbour networks are projected to be net exporters to the Hynetwork system which expects to require >99.5% feed-in specification. Note that should the Hynetwork specification would become >98% instead of >99.5%, the sweet spot would remain unchanged due to the >99.5% industrial feedstock requirements.

In 2050 we also see a broad sweet spot for the harbour network from 98% to 99.7% for three out of four scenarios and also a sweet spot appear around >99.9+ vol%, but we assume that this specification will likely be too challenging for the DSO to transport and guarantee to mobility end users. Below 98% the costs rise strongly due to (intermittent) power producers unable to find tail gas applications and above 99.7% cost increase strongly due to LOHC and industrial byproduct producers now requiring PSA systems. Moreover, overall purification related costs are expected to be low (~0.1 €/kg transported) due to mobility sector relatively small and end users being able to find local tail gas applications. Moreover, these findings are similar for all scenarios and towards 2050 it is the power sector that dominates the purification costs below 98%.

Case 2: Rural hydrogen network:

1-8 bar - low density demand in (small) urban area (including built environment for heating purposes, personal mobility purposes via distribution hubs, small power generation units (CHP) and several single “cluster 6” industries). Network consists mostly of re-used natural gas pipelines with relative long connections- the hydrogen demand follows a seasonal pattern

For the rural network case study we see a much less pronounced and broader sweet spot between 98% and 99,5% , as these networks are dominated by electrolysis infeed (no purification needed) and mobility off-take (always purification needed). These two market players actually create a theoretical “sweet spot” around “99.99%” but distributing this hydrogen purity specification mainly via existing re-purposed infrastructure will

be infeasible. For the much broader technically feasible sweet spot, it is the residential boilers and the import from Hynetwork that sets a preference for specifications between 98% at the lower limit (residential boilers off-take) and 99.5% (import Hynetwork) at the upper limit. Towards 2050 it is the (intermittent) power sector that dominates the purification costs below their 98% specification. Uncertainty whether rural networks will import or export to Hynetwork pins the sweet spot at Hynetwork specification (99.5%).

Summarizing the techno-economic modelling concluded for the harbour network case study, a future proof market sweet spot for the grid purity level between 98% and 99.7%. The same applies for the rural network case study, where a technically feasible sweet spot is between 98% and 99.5%. The overarching outcome of both network analysis results in future proof sweet spot for high pressure distribution network ranging from 98vol% to 99.5vol%. Generally speaking , overall purification related costs in the sweet spot range are expected to be ~0.1 €/kg transported hydrogen. Outside the sweet spot range the cost level is a factor 2-3 higher.

Figure 4.2. Overarching result of techno-economic analysis (all scenarios, both network types)

In addition, it has been concluded from sensitivity analysis that none of below market uncertainties from a cost-model point of view will significantly alter any of the key insights:

- Alternative 2035 and 2050 market scenarios
- Regional networks with or without Hynetwork connection
- Hynetwork specification @ >98% instead of >99.5%
- Large uncertainties in the future market split of the various production and end use categories between Hynetwork / Harbor and Rural networks.
- Uncertainties in the role of direct transport from electrolyzer to mobility stations via tube trailers.
- Uncertainties in the underlying technical parameters.

Given all these uncertainties, it is, from a pure market cost point of view, most optimal to keep the hydrogen purity level in regional gas distribution levels on 8 and 16 bar for as well harbour area's and rural area's close to the HN specification (~99.5%) given the fact this provides the most freedom when boosting or importing hydrogen from Hynetwork and also given the insight that the 98.5% -99.6% level will be acceptable to both the bulk of the end users as well as the bulk of the producers.

Permeation is a permanent phenomenon where a gas, fluid or vapor “moves” through a barrier layer (like a pipeline wall). This process takes place in two directions: pressurized gas permeates through the pipe wall to the surrounding environment, and components from the environment (nitrogen and oxygen present in air and water present in the soil) permeate through the pipe wall into the (gaseous) flow. When transporting hydrogen, the components that permeate into the hydrogen flow affect the hydrogen quality.

In parallel a technical analysis of **the influence of permeation and desorption** on gas quality inside a hydrogen grid has been investigated. Both phenomena have an impact on the gas quality that can be supplied to the end-user. Permeation has a permanent effect while adsorption is limited to the beginning of the operational lifecycle.

Two different networks were modelled: an urban network and a rural network. The main difference is the grid topology; in the rural area the distances between connections are larger. Two different flow

scenarios are used: a low offtake scenario, where no gas flows for 14 days is assumed (similar to a current summer holiday), and a high offtake scenario (similar to a current winter day). The model shows that during for the worst-case scenario, consisting of 14 days without gas flow in the rural area, the gas quality would change from 100% at the entry point to 99.67% at the off taker. To guarantee a hydrogen purity of 99.9 vol% in this scenario, the gas can reside in the network for a maximum of 4 days and 5 hours. For a hydrogen purity of 99.5% this is around 21 days, and for a hydrogen purity of 99.0% it is around 42 days. The model has limitations and is strongly dependent on flows, pressures and grid lengths, which means that these values should be seen as indicative values.

The modelling results show that the largest **effects of permeation** are in the low-pressure network (30-200 mbar). This effect is expected to increase as low demand periods in summer will grow due to growing market penetration of hybrid heat pumps, isolation measures taken by home owners and the effect of induction cooking. At higher pressures (>1 bar), there is less incoming contamination (due to the greater wall thickness) and more gas inside the pipeline (due to the higher pressure) in which it mixes. The result of this is that permeation has a limited role in the high-pressure (1-16 bar) distribution networks. For a 100mm diameter pipeline of PE, the contents of the 8 bar (SDR11) line takes 20 times longer to reach the same percentage of impurities as a 100mbar (SDR26) pipeline.

Desorption refers to the release of components (e.g. THT) from a surface (pipe wall). It is the opposite of absorption where the substance adheres to the surface. In repurposed pipelines, trace components such as THT present in natural gas may be absorbed to the pipe wall. When the pipelines are re-used for hydrogen transport, these components may slowly be released (desorbed) from the pipe wall and end up in the hydrogen flow. Consequently, due to this desorption the hydrogen quality is affected.

Additionally, it was concluded that the **effect of desorption** is limited to the starting period of the pipeline lifecycle, which can be solved by agreements or technical solutions. THT, used for odorization of natural gas, could pose a challenge when using repurposed pipeline, especially if the end-user utilizes a fuel cell. If this use-case presents itself, it should be further investigated. for example, desorption of THT in repurposed pipelines could result in THT levels maximum 10 ppm in the gas.

Challenges when managing future hydrogen distribution networks

The above described results of the market techno-economic study and the infrastructural material study serve as basis for future hydrogen distribution management.

Figure 4.3 illustrated the effect of permeation on the hydrogen purity in the grid in a worst case (long duration no flow) at low pressure purity level. In case of no (very limited) gas flows for 14 days the hydrogen purity drops due permeation from 100% at entry point to 99.67% at the customers end (resulting in 3322 ppm impurities in the hydrogen). This worst case situation (low flow) is illustrated indicatively as point 1 in figure 4.3.

When transferring this insight to a no gas flow case and an entry hydrogen specification of 99.5%, permeation would result in an exit hydrogen purity level of 98% after 60-70 days on low pressure distribution grid (point 2 in figure 4.3). Similarly, if the hydrogen entry purity level is 98%, after 60-70 days of no gas flow, a 96.5% hydrogen purity exit level will be reached. To our current knowledge this is not acceptable for existing burner applications. Further research is recommended on this topic.

Furthermore it can be derived from figure 4.3 that a hydrogen distribution network needs a minimum window (bandwidth) in order to meet the required hydrogen purity level at all the end-users. This means that relatively low (e.g. 98%) hydrogen purity intake from HN could result in off-spec hydrogen in the low pressure part of the network. Therefore a careful situation of the hydrogen purity levels is required. Alternatively further investigation can be done to understand the minimum required hydrogen purity for end use equipment.

Figure 4.3. Effect permeation on hydrogen purity in worst case (long duration no flow) at low pressure purity level

The result of the analyse haven been merged in a future hydrogen network vision. Figure 4.4 presents the following three grid pressure levels:

- Transmission network (>30 bar – newly build and repurposed steel pipelines)
- High pressure distribution network (1-16 bar – repurposed and newly build steel and PE pipelines)
- Low pressure distribution/network (30-200 mbar – repurposed and new PE and PVC pipelines)

As concluded from chapters 2 and 3 the high pressure distribution grid preferably has the same purity level as the HN network: (cluster 1). For newly build 1-16 bar pipeline networks this is feasible. For the 1-8 bar re-purposed pipelines, practical experience with existing distribution networks in which contaminants occur such as mine dust, residual natural gas components and components from the environment (oxygen, nitrogen and water) is needed to verify the modelled results. The low pressure part (30-200 mbar, cluster 2) of the distribution network cannot be on the same level as cluster 1 due impact of permeation. A dedicated purity specification is needed for this level.

Figure 4.4 shows some network management restriction as well. Due to different purity levels between cluster 1 and 2 a reverse flow from low pressure distribution networks towards the high pressure distribution network is not possible without additional purification. And, as the capacity of the low pressure distribution network is limited local infeed is rather limited to impossible. A third issue to address is that a reverse flow from distribution network towards transmission level need to be de-odorised. Further insights in the technology readiness and cost of such technology is needed.

Figure 4.4. Concept of two purity levels in hydrogen networks.

5. Monitoring and Measuring Protocol for hydrogen infeed

In previous chapters the first insights for a specification for the hydrogen distribution networks have been provided. Once the entry and exit hydrogen specifications for the distribution network are formulated, a solid infeed protocol to measure and monitor the hydrogen quality from hydrogen producers is needed. This infeed protocol ensures that the produced hydrogen is compatible with the hydrogen specifications.

A monitoring and measurement protocol offers a document that;

- provides clarity to the hydrogen producer about the requirements for their installation and operations,
- offers the network operator the ability to perform checks in a clear and measurable manner, thus forming an important basis for monitoring the hydrogen quality in the network.

Currently, a monitoring and measurement protocol for hydrogen network is not available. Based on the Dutch biomethane protocol [23], this chapter describes the elementary blocks for a Monitoring and Measuring Protocol for dynamic feed-in of hydrogen, based on the actual supply and demand. The aimed future protocol consists out of two parts:

- regulatory aspects
- technical aspects

The regulatory aspects are addressed in HyDelta 3 Work package 4 [24] where a list of topics are given that need to be resolved in the current legislation. In this work package we focus on the technical aspects.

5.1 Technical aspects

In addition to the regulatory aspects that need to be arranged, there is also a need for a document that sets out the practical requirements concerning the feed-in. Currently, this document is not available. In this study a first attempt is made based on the Measuring and Control Protocol (“Beheersprotocol”) for biomethane in the Netherlands [23].

Principles

The responsibility for delivering the correct gas quality and quantity lies with the feed-in party, while the grid operator has the task to make sure the required gas quality specifications are met. The measurements can be divided into:

- **Custody transfer measurements**, which form the basis for the financial compensation of the quantity of energy supplied.
- **Safety measurements**, to ensure that no additional risks (such as safety risks and malfunctioning of end-use equipment) are expected due to the presence of components in the hydrogen.

Figure 5.1 shows the relationship schematically. This protocol provides clarity to the feed-in party about the requirements that are imposed on its installation and operations and offers the grid operator the opportunity to carry out the checks in a clear and measurable manner. Clarity is also provided about the actions to be followed if the hydrogen to be fed in does not meet the required conditions.

Figure 5.1.: Schematic relationship of the various measurements

5.2 Continuous measurements

The accuracy of a measured result depends on factors. In Figure 5.2 a schematic representation of all the parameters that influence the uncertainty of the measurement are displayed. If the procedures described in this protocol are met, the measurement result is assumed to be error-free in the further considerations.

Figure 5.2.: Schematic representation of the entire (measurement) uncertainty chain.

As already mentioned above, many regulatory and technical aspects are not known at the moment of writing this report. In those cases, assumptions were made based on current legislations (laws and codes) that are now in use for natural gas and biomethane.

5.2.1 Gas Quantity

The gas quantity measurements are carried out by a therefor Recognised Party ('Erkend Meetverantwoordelijke'). This party is responsible for the correct operation and the timely execution of the validation and/or (re)calibration. The uncertainty of the total energy measurement depends on the maximum quantity of gas to be injected, as shown in Table 5.1 and Table 5.2.

The calorific value of hydrogen is typically three times lower as compared to the value for natural gas. This difference in calorific value has consequences for the uncertainty specifications, either for quantity (m³n/h) or energy (MJ) determination;

- Similar demands as biomethane on quantity (m³n/hr) results in higher uncertainty with respect to energy delivered (MJ) → will customers accept this?
- Similar demands as biomethane on energy (MJ) results in stricter demands with respect to quantity (m³n/h) → can metering equipment meet this requirement? [25]

The values shown in Table 5.1 and Table 5.2 are taken from the monitoring and control protocol for biomethane. Given the difference in calorific value between hydrogen and biomethane, the values shown in the tables below may be different.

Table 5.1. Uncertainty specifications gas quantity measurements of new installations for biomethane [23]

Capacity	Uncertainty volume measurement Biomethane (%relative) *)	
	$Q_{min}-0.2Q_{max}$	$0.2Q_{max}-Q_{max}$
< 40 m ³ (n)/h	5.7	5.3
< 40 m ³ (n)/h – 170.000 m ³ (n)/year	4.1	3.2
170.000-10.000.000 m ³ (n)/year	2.2	1.3
>10.000.000 m ³ (n)/year	1.5	1.0

*) 95% confidence interval

Table 5.2. Uncertainty specifications gas quantity measurements of existing installations for biomethane [23]

Capacity	Uncertainty volume measurement Biomethane (%relative) *)	
	$Q_{min}-0.2Q_{max}$	$0.2Q_{max}-Q_{max}$
< 40 m ³ (n)/h	7.7	6.3
< 40 m ³ (n)/h – 170.000 m ³ (n)/year	5.0	3.6
170.000-10.000.000 m ³ (n)/year	3.8	2.8
>10.000.000 m ³ (n)/year	1.5	1.0

*) 95% confidence interval

The compressibility factor (z) is required for the conversion to standard conditions. This must be calculated using an equation of state that includes hydrogen (up to 100%). Please note that AGA-8 equation of state as proposed in the monitor and control protocol for biomethane is limited for mixtures containing up to 10% hydrogen. Therefore, for calculation of the compressibility factor for hydrogen another equation of state (e.g. GERG2008 [26] or GL [27]) is recommended.

Questions, assumptions and remarks:

- Assuming that a Recognised Party will be in charge for the flow part, similar as is the case for natural gas and biomethane
- Which standards are applicable for calculating the compressibility of hydrogen?
- The energy content of hydrogen is approximately 1/3 of natural gas. Should the uncertainties of the volume measurements have to be compensated for this?

5.2.2 Gas composition

General

Depending on the level of pollutants ('trace components'), hydrogen is classified into clusters similar as was done for biomethane. Since the final specification for the distribution network is yet unknown, a list of relevant components and physical properties was made on the available gas (hydrogen and natural gas) specifications available in the Netherlands (see also **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**).

The concentration of the pollutants used in this study is indicated by the "used" column in the table below.

Table 5.3. Overview (concept) hydrogen specifications in the Netherlands

	Supposed specifications (by Kiwa and DNV)			Probability (+ = relevant to network, - = not relevant to network)		Origin and remarks					
	Used		RNB	LNB	HNS		MR aardgas website ^{h)}	LNB	RNB		
	Report	Date	GT-200157 website ^{g)}	GT-230144 website ^{g)}	01-08-24		30-11-24				
Gaseous components	Unit										
Hydrogen	mol%	98 - 100	≥98	>99.5	>99.5	<0.5		+	+		Origin
Inerts (N ₂ , He + Ar)	mol%	<0.5		<0.5	<0.5						Chemical processes, gas grid
Inerts (He + Ar)	mol%										
Nitrogen	mol%										
Oxygen	mol%	<0.2	<0.2	<0.001	<0.001	<0.5		+	+		Chemical processes, gas grid
Carbon dioxide	mol%	<0.002	<0.002	<0.002	<0.002	<10.3		+	+		Chemical processes, gassification
Carbon monoxide	molppm	≤2320	≤2320	≤20	≤20	≤2320		+	+		Chemical processes, gassification
Anorganic sulfur compounds (H ₂ S + COS)	molppm	≤3	≤3	≤3	≤3	≤3		+	+		Chemical processes
Organo sulfur compounds	mg S/m ³ (n)		≤6			≤6		-	-		
Total sulfur (peak value, excl. odorant)	mg S/m ³ (n)		≤20			≤20		-	-		
Total sulfur (yearly average, excl. odorant)	mg S/m ³ (n)		<5.5	≤3 molppm	≤3 molppm	<5.5		-	-		
Hydrocarbons (incl. CH ₄)	mol%	<0.5		<0.5	<0.5			+	+		Chemical processes, gassification, gas grid
Higher hydrocarbons (C ₂ ⁺ , incl. tar and oil)	mol% propane equivalent					≤5		+	+		Chemical processes, gassification, gas grid
Ammonia	molppm	≤10		≤10							Hydrogen carrier
Formic acid	molppm	≤10		≤10				+	+		Chemical processes
Formaldehyde	molppm	≤10		≤10				+	+		Chemical processes
Halogen compounds	molppb	≤50		≤50				+	-		Chemical processes
Silicium compounds	mg S/m ³ (n)					≤0.1		-	-		
Physical property	Unit										Remarks
Wobbe-index (ZSC/OC)	MJ/m ³ (n)	44.35-48.35 ^{A)}	44.85-48.35	45.99-48.35	45.99-48.35	43.46-44.41		+	+		> 98% used, divided into 3 clusters
Gas condensate	mg/m ³ (n) bij -3 °C		≤80			≤80		-	-		
Water dewpoint	°C @ bar	≤-8 @70 bar(g)	≤-10 @ 8 bar(a)	≤-8 @70 bar(g)	≤-8 @70 bar(g)	≤-10 @ 8 bar(a)		+	+		
Temperature	°C	5-20	5-20	5-30	5-30	5-20		+	+		
Particulates (> 5 µm)	mg/m ³ (n)		≤100			≤100		+	+		
Pathogenic microbes	counts/m ³ (n)					≤500		-	-		
Odorant	Unit										
THI-content	mg/m ³ (n)					10-40		-	+		
Sulfur free odorant	mg/m ³ (n)							-	+/		
Other impurities											

In this study four purity clusters were defined which are graphically shown in

A. The Wobbe-index should be at least 44.35 MJ/m³(n), independent of the measuring frequency due to end use appliances. (see report GT-200157).

B. Maximum amount depending on the Wobbe-index.

C. Shall not contain solid, liquid or gaseous material that might interfere with the integrity or operation of pipes or any gas appliance

D. <https://www.hynetwork.nl/media/10141014/indicative-quality-and-temperature-specification.pdf>

E. <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BVBR0035367/2023-12-02#511a0e2>

Figure 5.3 as function of the hydrogen purity (vol%) and Wobbe Index (MJ/m³n).

Figure 5.3. Schematic overview of purity cluster classification

In European and ISO standards a minimum Wobbe index of 44.35 MJ/m³n is mentioned based on the assumption that end-use appliances containing burners in the domestic market can handle a bandwidth of 4 MJ/m³n (44.35 – 48.35 MJ/m³n). In the near future, possible hydrogen qualities with hydrogen purity levels below 98% may be distributed. Consequently, this means that in this case Wobbe indices below the minimum Wobbe index value of 44.35 MJ/m³n will be distributed. At this moment it is unclear whether this gas will be distributed to a dedicated industry or that end-use equipment can handle a Wobbe bandwidth broader than 4 MJ/m³n.

For now it is assumed that in case of delivering a hydrogen purity below 98 mol% (cluster 4, see Figure below) to the consumers, the gas quality will be specified in a bilateral agreement between supplier and consumer. Therefore, cluster 4 is not included in this study.

For the input of the protocol, the three following different hydrogen concentration ranges are proposed:

- **Cluster 1 : 99.9 – 100 mol% H₂**, representing the hydrogen quality from electrolyzers
- **Cluster 2: 99.5 – 99.9 mol% H₂**, representing hydrogen quality from electrolyzers contaminated with trace components from the (reused) natural gas grid
- **Cluster 3: 98 – 99.5 mol% H₂**, representing the hydrogen quality from all types of production locations (chemical processes, electrolyzers, gasification, and so on). The minimum of 98 mol% is mentioned in many European and ISO specifications [22, 28, 29]

Table 5.4 shows the proposed maximum concentrations for the three proposed clusters. Here, only the components that are present at levels of at least 0.1 mol% (1000 molppm) and are expected to significantly contribute to the Wobbe index and calorific value are taken into account.

It should be noted that in the proposed TSO specification nitrogen, argon and helium are specified together as inerts. In this study a distinction is made between nitrogen on one side and argon (and helium) on the other side, since nitrogen can be present in all types of processes and air. Also, the effect of argon on the Wobbe index is much stronger than the effect of helium. Therefore, only argon is taken into account in the calculations of the gas composition for each cluster.

The effect of hydrocarbons on the Wobbe index is taken into account by dividing the hydrocarbons into methane and non-methane (calculated as propane equivalent).

Table 5.4. Proposed cluster classification (Custody Transfer Measurements)

Cluster	1	2	3
H ₂ -concentration (mol%)	H ₂ ≥99.9	99.5<H ₂ <99.9	98≤H ₂ ≤ 99.5
Inert (Argon) (mol%)	0.05	0.1	0.1
Nitrogen (mol%)	0.05	0.1	0.8
Methane (mol%)	0	0	0.5
Propane equivalent (mol%)	0	0.3	0.5
Carbon monoxide (mol %)	0	0	0.1
Wobbe Index (MJ/m ³ n)	47.92 – 48.35	47.07 – 47.92	44.35 – 47.07

The gaseous components shown in **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** are divided into custody transfer parameters and safety related parameters. Generally speaking, all components with a concentration above 0.1 mol% (1000 molppm) will contribute to the calorific value and Wobbe index, and therefore will be seen as custody transfer parameters. For safety related parameters, a distinction is made based on the concentration levels; 100-1000 molppm an uncertainty of 10% (relative) is assumed and for <100 molppm an uncertainty of 20% (relative) is assumed.

The need to measure a trace component continuously is depending on the concentration level and the possible impact of that component has on safety aspects. Trace components that have to be measured continuously have to meet one or more of the following criteria:

1. The concentration of the component is at a level where it is of influence on the Wobbe-index
2. The concentration level of the component has a negative impact on safety aspects (such as grid pollution by tar (from gasification) and performance degradation of fuel cells caused by sulphur poisoning).

Continuous measuring is defined as: measuring with a frequency of 5 minutes maximum, so at least 12 datapoints will be achieved during 1 hour measuring.

Since the concentrations levels of all components vary from mol% to molppm level, not all components can be measured with the same instrument. Therefore the measuring setup will be built up from a set of different instruments or sensors that have their own calibration procedure and maintenance interval. In Table 5.6 the specifications per cluster is displayed.

Depending on the origin of the hydrogen, there might be no need to measure all of the listed components. In the Connection Agreement ('aansluitovereenkomst') the list of components and measuring techniques should be listed.

5.3 Custody Transfer

The specifications for (superior) calorific value and Wobbe-index for natural gas are laid down in a regulatory frame work consisting of Dutch Gas Act (Gaswet [30]), Codes [31, 32] and Ministerial Regulations [33]. Similarly, the specification for the (superior) calorific value and the Wobbe Index for hydrogen should also be laid down in a similar future regulatory frame work. In the table below, the uncertainty of the energy related parameters are shown for biomethane. As discussed above, these values may be different given the difference in calorific value for hydrogen and natural gas (biomethane).

Table 5.5. Specifications energy related parameters

	Unit *)	Uncertainty
Wobbe-index (W)	MJ/m ³ (n)	≤0.5% relative
Superior calorific value (Hs)	MJ/m ³ (n)	≤0.4% relative

*) Volume at 0 °C en 101.325 kPa and energy content at 25 °C.

calculation of the Wobbe index and superior calorific value must be done in accordance with ISO 6976 (table 2 in ISO norm: 0oC, 101.325 kPa and table 3 in ISO norm: 25°C or table 5 in ISO norm: 25/0°C) [34]. For the calculation of the Wobbe index the total composition (total share) is taken into account. In HyDelta work package 4 [35] a recommendation towards standardization of hydrogen metrics is made, based on interviews and discussion with the industry. From this, it was recommended to use the hydrogen share (hydrogen content only) for calculating remuneration of the delivered hydrogen.

Questions, assumptions and remarks:

- Uncertainty values taken over from natural gas. Question is of these values have to be changed for hydrogen since the energy content for hydrogen is 1/3.
- It was suggested to take only the H₂ content into account for custody transfer.

Table 5.6. Proposed specification for calibration gases custody transfer

All concentrations on molar basis.

Component		Hydrogen (H ₂)	Oxygen (O ₂)	Nitrogen (N ₂)	Methane (CH ₄)	Higher hydrocarbons (as C ₃ H ₈)	Inerts (He + Ar)	Carbon monoxide
Cluster #1								
Measuring instrument	Range	99.9-100	0-0.1	0-0.1			0-0.1	
	Detection limit		0.01	0.01			0.01	
Calibration gas	Concentration	99.85	0.05	0.05			0.05	
	Uncertainty	1% rel.	10% rel.	10% rel.			10% rel.	
Cluster #2								
Measuring instrument	Range	99.5-99.9	0-0.1	0-0.2		0-0.3	0-0.1	
	Detection limit		0.01	0.01		0.01	0.01	
Calibration gas	Concentration	99.4	0.1	0.2		0.2	0.1	
	Uncertainty	1% rel.	10% rel.	10% rel.		10% rel.	10% rel.	
Cluster #3								
Measuring instrument	Range	98-99.5	0-0.2	0-0.2	0-0.5	0-0.5	0-0.1	0-0.2
	Detection limit		0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Calibration gas	Concentration	97.9	0.1	0.8	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1
	Uncertainty	1% rel.	10% rel.	10% rel.	10% rel.	10% rel.	10% rel.	10% rel.

Some notes regarding the measurement and calibration :

- Feed-in party must demonstrate that the selected calibration gases and the validation and/or calibration frequency can meet the specifications. Therefore, the calibration and validation data should be recorded in control charts (similar as is done for biomethane). Calibration is only necessary if the results show that drift is without the boundaries.
- The feed-in don't have to be interrupted during the calibration or validation procedure.
- The maximum end date and minimal pressure as specified by the supplier of the calibration gases may not be exceeded.
- If the results indicate that a component is outside the boundary values, the feed-in should be stopped.

5.4 Proposed safety related parameters

Next to the custody transfer components (see previous paragraph), the safety related parameters should be measured. In case the safety related parameter is also part of the custody transfer components, the specifications as mentioned in **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** prefer. The specifications are listed in *Table 5.7*. Deviations from the table are acceptable, provided that feed-in party can demonstrate that the alternative measuring technique complies with the specification.

Table 5.7. Proposed specifications physical properties

**) depending on the pressure of the grid (bilateral agreement)*

	Specification	Measuring range	Uncertainty	Standard
Carbon monoxide (CO)	2320 ppm	0..5000 ppm	20% relative	NEN 12039
Hydrogen sulphide (H ₂ S)	3 ppm	0..5 ppm	20% relative	Electrochemical
Water dewpoint	-8 °C @ 70 bar(a)	-50..20 °C	<1 °C @ 70 bar(a)	ISO 6327 [36]
Pressure	*) bar(a)	1..17 bar(a)	< 0.05 bar(a)	ISO 15970 [37]
Temperature	5..30 °C	-5..40 °C	< 0.5 °C	ISO 15970 [37]

Calibration, validation or maintenance should comply to the specifications of the supplier.

Questions, assumptions and remarks:

Values taken over from **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** and appendix 2 of the Regeling Gaskwaliteit [33]

5.5 Odorization

Whether the hydrogen should be odorized is depending on the gas grid and should be recorded in the Connection Agreement, as well as the concentration level and the odorant to be used.

In case of odorization, feed-in party has to demonstrate that the odorization unit is operating within specifications. The operation of the system as well as the control measures must be recorded in the Measuring protocol and must be approved by the grid operator.

Possible checks might be:

- Flow switch: to determine the (liquid) odorant is pumped into the system and no air bubbles are present
- Pump: signal that the pump is working
- Mass flow controller: to ensure that the measured flow value is within acceptable boundaries of the setpoint
- Measurement of the concentration: continuous using a sensor or discontinuous by taking samples

5.6 Periodic measurement

The custody transfer components and safety related parameters require a continuous measurement. Depending on the concentration level, the impact of the component and the costs for measuring, not all components as mentioned in **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** have to be part of the continuous measurements in the gate keeper. Since the feed-in party should demonstrate that all specifications are met frequent measurements (frequency to be discussed, but for example once every three months). These measurements should be carried out by a therefore certified laboratory.

In Table 5.8 below, a proposal for the components for periodic measurements are shown, including the proposed custody transfer components (Table 5.6) and safety parameters (Table 5.7).

Table 5.8. Proposal for custody transfer components, safety parameters and components for periodic measurements.

		Used	Custody transfer	Safety parameters	Periodic
Gaseous components	Unit				
Hydrogen	mol%	98 - 100	X		
Inerts (He + Ar)	mol%	< 0.5	X ^{F)}		X ^{G)}
Nitrogen	mol%	B)	X ^{F)}		X ^{G)}
Oxygen	mol%	< 0.2	X ^{F)}		X ^{G)}
Carbon dioxide	mol%	< 0.002			X
Carbon monoxide	molppm	≤ 2320	X ^{F)}	X ^{G)}	
Anorganic sulfur compounds (H ₂ S + COS)	molppm	≤ 3		X	
Hydrocarbons (incl. CH ₄)	mol%	< 0.5	X ^{F)}		X ^{G)}
Higher hydrocarbons (C ₂ ⁺ , incl. tar and oil)	mol% propane equivalent	B)	X ^{F)}		X ^{G)}
Ammonia	molppm	≤ 10			X
Formic acid	molppm	≤ 10			X
Formaldehyde	molppm	≤ 10			X
Halogen compounds	molppb	≤ 50			X
Physical property	Unit				
Wobbe-index (25C/0C)	MJ/m ³ (n)	44.35 - 48.35 ^{A)}	X		
Water dewpoint	C @ bar	≤ -8 @70 bar(g)		X	
Temperature	C	5 - 20		X	
Pressure	Bar (a)	1 - 17		X	
Odorant	Unit				
Odorant content	mg/m ³ (n)			X ^{H)}	X ^{I)}
Other impurities					

A. The Wobbe-index should be at least 44.35 MJ/m³(n), independant of the measuring frequency due to end use appliances. (see report GT-200157).

B. Maximum amount depending on the Wobbe-index.

C. Shall not contain solid, liquid or gaseous material that might interfere with the integrity or operation of pipes or any gas appliance

D. <https://www.hynetwerk.nl/media/jokhjtcbl/indicative-quality-and-temperature-specification.pdf>

E. <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0035367/2023-12-02#Bijlage2>

F. In case ≥ 1000 molppm

G. In case < 1000 molppm

H. Supplier should prove that odorant is sufficiently injected in accordance with the specifications

I. Concentrations measurements to assure that the odorant content meets the specification

Questions, assumptions and remarks:

Measurement frequency to be determined.

6. Summary, conclusions and suggestions for future research

6.1 Summary and conclusions

This HyDelta work package aims to deliver insights (both technical and economical) into cost optimal and feasible specifications for hydrogen distribution grids in order to support operators in substantiating their strategies for feed-in, offtake and monitoring and controlling the agreed hydrogen quality.

Defining a hydrogen quality network specification is a complex task, in which many interests need to be weighed against each other against a background of various techno-economical limitations and possible solutions. To provide guidance on the (future) hydrogen specification, the research activities focussed on the following 3 elements:

- A. Hydrogen purity level for the distribution networks based on a techno-economical market modelling analysis.
- B. Technical network limitations e.g. the effects of permeation and desorption on hydrogen quality in distribution networks.
- C. Managing hydrogen quality in future hydrogen networks (combining inputs from part A and B), including hydrogen infeed monitoring and measurement protocol

The techno-economic analysis provides insight into the optimal purity specification (sweet spot) of hydrogen in the high pressure section of the future distribution network from a market point of view. A high level market wide techno-economic analysis has been performed on seven projected production and off take scenarios for the years 2035 and 2050. Two different networks configurations were defined (a harbour and a rural network) for which the techno-economical modelling was performed. The overarching model outcome of both network types result in a future-proof sweet spot for high pressure distribution network ranging from 98 to 99.5%.

In parallel – of the techno-economic market modelling – a technical analysis of the effect of pipeline transport on hydrogen purity is performed. In repurposed distribution pipelines, contaminants such as residual natural gas components (THT, aromatics and alkanes) can be present that may affect the hydrogen quality. Also, permeation of pollutants from the environment (water, nitrogen and oxygen) may affect both repurposed and newly built pipelines.

A model was developed to investigate the effect of these contaminants on the hydrogen quality. From the model results it was concluded that the effect of desorption is limited to the starting period of the pipeline lifecycle. However, permeation of pollutants in the low pressure distribution network (30-200 mbar) was identified to have a significant effect on the hydrogen purity. Especially, in case there is (almost) no flow (comparable with the current natural gas offtake in summer), permeation can lead to a significant amount of impurities in the hydrogen.

At higher pressures (>1 bar), the impact on hydrogen purity is limited as there is less incoming contamination (due to the greater wall thickness) and more gas inside the pipeline (due to the higher pressure) in which it mixes.

The results of both techno-economical modelling and technical analysis of the effect of transport on hydrogen quality are brought together into a vision on future hydrogen network set-up. From the results of the techno-economical and transport modelling it is concluded that two cluster of dedicated purity specification are needed in the distribution network:

- **Cluster 1:** Newly built high pressure distribution grids above 1 bar preferably follow the purity level of the HN network. Repurposed pipelines above 1 bar might have some challenges in delivering the required hydrogen purity level. Further research is needed on existing distribution networks in which contaminants exist such as mine dust, residual natural gas components and components from the environment (oxygen, nitrogen and water).
- **Cluster 2:** The low pressure part (30-200 mbar) of the distribution network has challenges to guarantee the minimal purity level as required by the end-users on all locations 100% of the time. Especially in situations with (almost) no flow (comparable with the current natural gas offtake in summer) the impact of permeation on the hydrogen purity level for this part of the network is significant. This all calls for a separate purity specification for this level.

Due to different purity levels between cluster 1 and 2 a reverse flow from low pressure distribution networks towards the high pressure distribution network is very unlikely or will require purification. And, as the capacity of the low pressure distribution network is limited, local infeed is rather limited to impossible. A third issue to address is that a reverse flow from distribution network towards transmission level needs to be de-odorised. Further insights in the technology readiness and cost of such technology is needed.

6.2 Future research suggestions

During the course of this work, a myriad of new insights have been gained on the topic of hydrogen quality specifications for regional networks, both as a result of the analysis and the biweekly discussions with the network operator experts. The new insights may concern 1) suggestions for further research topics including innovative ways to manage future regional hydrogen quality challenges. 2) possible improvement on the modeling approach.

On the level of **how to manage hydrogen quality future regional gas distribution networks**, following research questions can be distilled:

- How can we connect the non-odorized HN network to the odorized regional gas network and then also facilitate reverse flow from the regional network to the HN network (depicted in the figure as "odo / de-odo" unit)? The state of the art of such technology needs to be investigated. And what costs are involved?
- The regional gas network operator in the Netherlands currently has a legal obligation to apply odorization. One could ask the question if another odorization policy could be a possibility. E.g. not to odorize the 1-16 bar distribution networks. What are the risks and considerations if you decide to apply an alternative odorization regime for hydrogen?
- Possibly the HN hydrogen specification will not be >99.5% (as currently suggested) but 98%. An entry of 98% hydrogen purity in the distribution network means that the purity level on the low pressure exit points might go significantly below 98%. The question is to what extent the hydrogen purity exit level can be lowered. This will give crucial insights on the minimum hydrogen purity entry level. Is 98% technically the minimum for specific end users, or can they handle lower purity levels? Most of the connected equipment in this network segment are

residential heating boilers. Research is needed to determine what a realistic value is in practice.

- Further research is needed on the impact of impurities on the hydrogen specification:
 - oxygen ingress (permeation) in PE and PVC pipes by comparing the modelling with experimental data acquired from (for example) demonstration project to validate the model used in this study.
 - Other impurities that may be present in repurposed pipelines and have not been investigated in this study such as (see also Chapter 3):
 - particulates, such as rust, dust, etc.
 - water, condensates, oils etc.
 - possible nitric and hydrogen cyanide acids

Furthermore, there might be innovative ways to mitigated hydrogen purity issues via smart networks design, controlled via measurement protocols and counteracted with special measures:

- As for smart design, it is to be advised to create differentiated network entry/exit specifications to customers connected to the high pressure bidirectional sections, exchanging with HN, and customers in the low pressure unidirectional section supplying boilers and engines.
- Entry specifications could be more strict than the exit specifications, thus creating operational margin for the significant hydrogen <-> pipeline wall interactions along the long distribution lines during the low flow summer periods.
- Special measures could be introduced to enforce a minimum summer network flow, such as letting a gas engines purge the content of the rural hydrogen network running at periodic intervals. This is similar to weekly legionella prevention in hot sanitation water storages using electric heat elements.

On the level of **improving the modelling approach** the following can be shared. All models are simplifications of the real world and the hydrogen purity cost model used in this work has limitations (see Appendix A) which are all deliberate choices to keep the already quite extensive model as simple and manageable as possible. For example, the market cost model is “static” i.e. the calculations are based on annual volumes and this does not capture world conditions like intermittent electrolyzer production and seasonal residential demand. The impact of this modelling choice is minor, but it is an issue that could be addressed if considered necessary.

As for the pipeline permeation and desorption model, it is now based the average pipeline lengths, summer/ winter conditions, and permeation/ desorption rates. One could however argue that the hydrogen purity specifications should perhaps be based not on the average situations but on worst case scenarios that could occur under real world conditions. If considered of value, this issue can be addressed in subsequent HyDelta work.

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Appendix A. Limitations of the hydrogen purity cost model

The model used in this work has the following known limitations:

- The model is “static” i.e. it uses annual volumes and does not include hourly data on hydrogen supply, demand, storage and interactions with HN. This is a deliberate choice as it would seriously affect the model performance.
- The model assumes “continuous stirred vessel” operation assuming random scattering of suppliers and end users along the network.
- The model concerns the bidirectional high pressure section of the regional networks and assumes identical entry and exit specifications in terms of minimum required hydrogen content.
- The model does not model interactions of the hydrogen with the pipeline internal walls, causing the transported hydrogen to pick up impurities along the way or after a significant period of standing still.
- The model models economics (CAPEX, OPEX and hydrogen values losses) in a highly simplistic manner. There are no inflation corrections, taxes, Levelized costs of capital etc.
- The model assumes a green field investment approach to the required PSA systems both in 2035 and in 2050, i.e. there is no re-use of existing installations assumed.
- The approach assumes that the hydrogen purity related costs may be considered as “add-ons” to the significantly larger hydrogen commodity cost, just as network fees, compression costs, storage costs, and handling fees need to be paid by “someone somewhere along the value chain”. In the real world however, these costs would impact suppliers and end users differently and would (slightly) affect the underlying supply-demand scenario. If producers need to supply 99.9% pure hydrogen as a “service” to the “demanding” industrial & mobility end users, this will stimulate these end user segments but unfortunately also negatively impact the “less demanding” end users using boilers. These minor market feedback loops are not included in the model.
- A significant part of the hydrogen purity cost is associated with tail gas production of PSA separation stages. PSA systems split an incoming hydrogen stream into a purified stream and a “tail gas” stream including hydrogen and the impurities, and this tail gas may represent an economic loss. Firstly, tail gas directly results in lower hydrogen sales for producers or an extra hydrogen procurement requirement for end users. Secondly, the tail gas still represents a remaining value as a source of heat, but only if producer or end user has a local (ideally on site) use case for this heat. Otherwise, tail gas may be “flared”. The model calculates the remaining tail gas values for all producer and end user segments by comparing it to the presumed lowest cost alternative source of heat, natural gas and CO₂ emission rights. The model thus inherently assumes that even in 2050, natural gas may still be considered as an economic alternative to market.
- All information we have on PSA operation assumes a known hydrogen feed with known impurities and the PSA system is tailored to filter these out. Filtering out hydrocarbons is relatively simple, filtering out inert components (especially noble gasses) is however hard. Installing PSA systems near end users, to filter out an uncertain amount of a wide range of possible impurities and knowing how often to regenerate the filter beds is uncharted territory. It might be that we underestimate PSA costs or overestimate the tail gas production at end user sites.
- There will be a wide range of additional factors that influence the eventual optimal regional network hydrogen specification that are outside the scope of the hydrogen purity cost model. On the low side (<97%) there may be issues with calorific content billing to small scale consumers if the hydrogen content fluctuates strongly. Also, the Wobbe value of hydrogen is very sensitive to (heavy) impurities, that might result in combustion instabilities in boilers and engines, and these may be an additional limiting factor. On the upper side (>99.5%) there may be issues in transporting hydrogen over longer distances or in stagnant pipeline sections due to wall outgassing of impurity infiltration from the environment. The exact definition of the limits is outside the scope of this study but will be addressed in follow-up research.

Appendix B. Calculation of THT concentration from mg/m³ to ppm

Concentratie THT in gas	36	mg/m ³
	0,036	g/m ³
Molecuulgewicht THT	88,17132	g/mol
	0,000408296	mol/m ³
Concentratie THT in gas	9,82161E-06	mol/mol
	9,821608741	ppm
	9821,608741	ppb
Moleculen per kuub gas		
Aangenomen ideaal gas		
PV=nRT		
n/V=P/(RT)		
Temperatuur (T)	20	°C
	293,15	K
Druk (P)	1	atm(a)
Gasconstante (R)	0,082057366	(L*atm)/(K*mol)
n/V	0,041571197	mol/liter
	41,57119691	mol/m ³